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of the Iraqi Ministry of Health

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Cancer in Iraq: Distribution by primary tumor site

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Abstract

Background: Little is known about the pattern of cancer in Iraq. The aim of this paper is to report the pattern of cancer in Iraq by primary tumor site in the largest series of Iraqi patients with cancer.

Patients and methods: During a five-year period (2000-2004) 63923 Iraqi patients, with various types of newly diagnosed cancer were registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk). 32281 patients were males (50.5%) and 31652 patients were females (49.5%).

Results: Breast was by far the most common site of cancer accounted for 16% of all Iraqi patients. Lungs and the bronchi were the second most common site of cancer and the first most common site in males. Cancer in the lung and bronchus accounted for 8% of all cancers. Leukemia was the third most common cancer in Iraq accounting for 7% of all cancers. The four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among males were cancers of the lung and bronchus, bladder, leukemia and Non-Hodgkin lymphoma (NHL), accounting for about 37.7% of estimated cancer cases in males.

The four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among females were cancers of the breast, leukemia, uterus (including cervix and corpus) and cancers of brain and CNS, accounting for about 47.5% of estimated cancer cases in females. Breast cancer alone is accounted for % (31%) of all new cancer cases among females.

Conclusion: The pattern of cancer in Iraq by primary tumor site is rather different from the pattern in other countries like USA, Nigeria and European countries.

Keywords: Cancer-Iraq-Primary site

Introduction

Cancer is a major public health problem worldwide [1]. In 2007 cancer was the third leading cause of deaths in Iraq and the 7th leading cause of morbidity [2]. Little is known about the pattern of cancer in Iraq. The need for comprehensive knowledge about cancer forms in Iraq is mandatory to plan and establish control programs for the common cancer which may be amenable to prevention, early detection and cure. The aim of this paper is to report the pattern of cancer in Iraq by primary tumor site in the largest series of Iraq patients with cancer.

Patients an methods: During a five-year period (2000-2004) 63923 Iraqi patients, with various types of newly diagnosed cancer were registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk). 32281 patients were males (50.5%) and 31652 patients were females (49.5%).

Results

Breast was the most common site of cancer accounted for 16% of all Iraqi patients. Lungs and the bronchi were the second most common site of cancer and the first most common site in males. Cancer in the lung and bronchus accounted for 8% of all cancers. Leukemia was the third most common cancer in Iraq accounting for 7% of all cancers. Table (1): Type of cancer by primary tumor site.

The four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among males were cancers of the lung and bronchus, bladder, leukemia and Non-Hodgkin lymphoma , accounting for about 37.7% of estimated cancer cases in males.

The four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among females were cancers of the breast, leukemia, uterus including cervix and corpus) and brain cancers and CNS, accounting for about 47.5% of estimated cancer cases in females. Breast cancer alone is accounted for % (31%) of all new cancer cases among females.

Figure (1) shows the 10 leading cancers by gender.

Discussion

The pattern of cancer in Iraq by primary tumor site is rather different from the pattern in other countries like USA. The

four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among males in the USA are cancers of the prostate, lung and bronchus, colon and rectum, and bladder, accounting for about 57% % of estimated cancer cases in males[3]. The four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among females in the USA are cancers of the breast, lung and bronchus, colon and rectum, and uterine corpus, accounting for about 56 % of estimated cancer cases in males [3].

Primary site	Total No	Male (%)	No Female (%)
Breast	10277	464(4.5%)	9813(95.5%)
Lung & bronchus	5157	4105(79.6%)	1052(20.4%)
Leukemia	4476	2618(58.5%)	1858(41.5%)
Bladder	4253	3250(76.4%)	1003(23.6%)
Brain & CNS	3871	2217(57.3%)	1654(42.7%)
NHL	3782	2283(60.4%)	1499(39.6%)
Colorectal	2736	1545(56.5%)	1191(43.5%)
Larynx	2590	1998(77%)	592(23%)
Skin excluding Melanoma	2425	1342(55.4%)	1083(44.6%)
Stomach	2108	1246(59%)	862(41%)
Uterus including Cervix and corpus)	1692	0	1692
Hodgkin disease	1502	925(61.6%)	577(38.4%)
Thyroid	1334	446(33.4%)	888(66.6%)
Kidney, pelvis& ureter	1232	754(61%)	478(39%)
Ovary	1203	0	1203
Prostate	1081	1081	0
Pancreas	1014	575(56.7%)	439(43.3%)
Bone & cartilage	999	58.7(58.8%)	412(41.2%)
Liver & bile ducts	637	358(56%)	279(44%)
Esophagus	539	342(63.5%)	197(36.5%)

Table (1): Type of cancer by primary tumor site

Male			Female	
Lung & bronchus	4105(12.7%)		Breast	9813 (31%)
Bladder	3250 (10%)	Leukemia	1858(6 %)	
Leukemia	2618 (8%)	Uterus including	1692 (5.3%)	
NHL	2283(7%)	Cervix and corpus)		
Brain &CNS	2217 (6.9%)	Brain &CNS	1654(5.2%)	
Larynx	1998(6%)	NHL	1499(4.7%)	
Colorectal	1545(4.8%)	Ovary	1203(3.8%)	
Skin excluding	1342 (4%)	Colorectal	1191 (3.8%)	
Melanoma		Skin excluding	1083(3.4%)	
Stomach	1246(3.9%)	Melanoma		
Prostate	1081(3.3%)	Lung & bronchus	1052((3.3)	
		Bladder	1003(3%)	

Figure (1): The 10 leading cancers by gender.

Cancer of the lung and bronchus is the second leading cause of cancer in the USA accounting for 15% of all newly diagnosed cancer in females.

This difference is obviously attributed to the high incidence of smoking in females in the USA. Cancer of the lung and bronchus in USA females accounted for a higher percentage than Iraqi males.

Cancer of the prostate is the leading cause cancer in males in the USA accounting for 29% of the newly diagnosed cases [3]. In Iraq Cancer of the prostate is the 10th leading cause cancer in males in the USA accounting for 3.3% of the newly diagnosed cases in males only. The continued increase in the incidence of prostatic cancer has been attributed to screening with prostate-specific antigen testing [4, 5].

The most common form of cancers in Europe are breast cancer (13.5% of all cancer cases), followed by colorectal cancers (12.9%) and lung cancer (12.1%) [6].

In Nigeria cancers of the cervix (22.9%), breast (18.9%), ovary (8.2%), non-melanoma skin cancer (6.3%), and uterus (6.2%) were the most frequent female cancers. In males, cancer of the prostate (16.5%), bladder (10.2%), non-melanoma skin (9.9%), colorectal (9.3%) and connective tissue (6.3%) were most common[7]. Cancer in Africa is not only different from the cancer pattern in Iraq but also differs from the pattern observed in USA and Europe.

Conclusion: The pattern of cancer in Iraq by primary tumor site is rather different from the pattern in other countries like USA, Nigeria and European countries. This provided an important information about cancer forms in Iraq is which can be useful in planning and establishing control programs for the common cancer which can be amenable to prevention, early detection and cure.

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War-related mental health disorders among Iraqis 10 years after the 1991 Gulf War: A comparative study of soldiers and civilians living under sustained socio-environmental stress

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Abstract

Background: Prior studies of mental health consequences of the Gulf War (GW) have been confined to Allied forces, limiting the ability to control for important geographically and culturally-related factors. We conducted an epidemiological mental health study among Iraqi soldiers and civilians who are still residing in Iraq. This group has been exposed to sustained socio-environmental stress.

Methods: A cross-sectional sample of 742 Iraqi GW veterans and 413 civilians responded to a validated mental health survey. The response rate was 96.3%. Mental health disorders, including post traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), were classified using both self-reports and validated scales. War-related exposure was calculated using the sum score of items assessing trauma exposure.

Results: Iraqi soldiers reported significantly more depression (Odds Ratio [OR] 4.9; 95% confidence interval [CI] 2.2-11.1) and anxiety (OR 3.9; 95% CI, 1.2-13.3) compared to civilians, adjusting for age, education, and smoking. Soldiers closest to Kuwait during the GW reported significantly more depression compared to soldiers deployed further away from the war epicenter (OR 104.6; 95% CI, 28.0-390.8) and anxiety (OR 4.1; 95% CI, 1.5-11.1). The highest self-reported trauma exposure occurred in the southwest of Iraq.

Conclusion: Iraqi soldiers that took part in the GW are at increased risk suffering from many of the same mental health disorders plaguing Allied soldiers. Soldiers closest to Kuwait were more at risk, suggesting a direct link to war-specific environmental exposures,

although self-reported trauma exposure was higher in the southwest of Iraq. The study offers additional insights into the mental health consequences of living under sustained socio-environmental stress, originating from the Iraqi war. The study points out socio-environmental factors worthy of further explorations.

Keywords: PTSD, depression, anxiety, war, Iraq, trauma

Introduction

Between August 1, 1990 to June 1, 1991, soldiers and support personnel from nearly fifty countries were engaged in the Gulf War (GW) Operation Desert Shield/Desert Storm. Following the war when veterans were returning to their native countries, there was an apparent increase in the number of soldiers reporting an array of mental and somatic symptoms [1-18]. Similar symptoms have been reported by soldiers deployed to other recent conflicts, including the 2003 invasion of Iraq, albeit more limited in the numbers affected [9-24]. Epidemiological studies have provided substantial evidence of an increased prevalence of PTSD, and other mental health disorders among GW veterans compared to non-deployed soldiers, or soldiers deployed to other conflicts [1, 11, 25-27]. Specifically, depressive disorders and PTSD have been reported to be more common among GW veterans as compared to veterans from the Afghanistan conflict [28].

Prior studies of mental health effects from the GW have almost exclusively involved Allied forces. There are a number of important confounders in such studies including the fact that deployed soldiers were not accustomed to the GW's regions geographical,

ethnic, cultural and microbial characteristics, neither desert climate.

The purposes of this study were two-fold. We wanted to determine whether: 1) Mental health disorders differ between Iraqi soldiers deployed during the 1991 Gulf War as compared to Iraqi civilians, and

2) Soldiers deployed closer to the war epicenter (presumed to have the highest trauma exposure history) exhibited more mental health disorders as compared to soldiers deployed further away.

The study provides new insights as to possible mental health effects from living under sustained socio-environmental stress, originating from the 1991 Gulf War and subsequent hardships, including oppression, unemployment, and lack of food.

Participants and Setting

A sample of men (women were not allowed to join the Iraqi military forces at this time) who were soldiers and civilians between 18-45 years of age in the Iraqi provinces of Basrah and Messan at the time of the 1991 GW and living within 300 Kilometers from Kuwait were eligible for study enrollment. Three surgical residents from Basrah University were trained to select and interview individuals who accompanied patients attending three outpatient clinics in the Basrah and Messan Provinces in Iraq. Thus, we interviewed persons that did not themselves seek out the health care centers. The three clinics were run by the Iraqi Ministry of Health and available to all Iraqis. All residents followed a standard algorithm to identify and interview participants. Potential participants were asked about their interest in participating in a health study of the GW. Participation was voluntary

and respondents were able to withdraw from the study at any time. Once verbal consent was obtained, the medical residents proceeded to ask each question and read their respective response choices in Arabic and recorded the participants' responses in the survey questionnaire. All interviews were done in a physician's office to ensure confidentiality.

A total of 1266 prospective participants that accompanied patients to the health centers were approached. Sixty-six (5.5%) refused to participate for the following reasons: no time (n=16), the patients they accompanied were critically ill or a child in need of constant attention (n=22), fear of reprisal from the regime (n=28).

Questionnaire content

A structured interviewer-administered questionnaire, which was based on the survey developed and used in several studies of large numbers of U.S. GW Veterans, was used [29, 30]. This questionnaire was initially designed and validated at the University of Iowa and the Iowa Department of Health and the Center for Disease Control. This original questionnaire was translated into Arabic and back-translated into English to ensure the validity of the phrasing of the questions. It has been validated among Iraqi refugees living in Michigan, US [31-33]. In the current study, we excluded a total of 24 questions from the original English version since 12 questions were not applicable, and an additional 12 questions were deemed culturally too sensitive, and not of relevance to the current study.

The questionnaire contained questions concerning socioeconomics, smoking history, age, height, and weight.

Residential or stationed distance from Kuwait was queried from the

participants. Distance from Kuwait was classified into three zones: zone₁ consisted of soldiers in Kuwait; zone₂, participants 100-199 kilometers from Kuwait; and zone₃, participants between 200-300 kilometers from Kuwait. Out of a total of 1200 respondents, 45 respondents were removed from the analysis due to the fact that they had resided between 300 to 860 kilometers from Kuwait. The final group thus consisted of 1155 participants. All participants reported the city or village in which they resided during the Gulf War. Based on this information we assigned a zone to the person based on distance from Kuwait.

War-related trauma exposure was assessed by asking whether participants had been exposed (yes or no) to one or more of the following (warning alarms for chemical exposures (received a weighted score of times 9; seen dead bodies and/or persons seriously disfigured, 10; personal exposures judged to be harmful or extremely stressful, 6; under fire from small fire arms, 10; had a scud missile explode in the air or on the ground within a perimeter of a 1 mile, 8; had artillery, rockets, mortars, or anything else, apart from scud missiles, explode within 1 mile, 8; suffered a war-related injury requiring medical attention during the war, 10; witnessed anyone dying, 10). These weighted item scores formed a scale. The aggregate, weighted score was used as a self-reported trauma exposure measure.

Self-reported mental health

The participants were asked to respond to whether they during the last year had had any of a number of specific psychiatric conditions diagnosed by a physician, including PTSD, depression, anxiety disorder, or other psychiatric

disorders, such as Schizophrenia. If they responded affirmative to any of the psychiatric conditions, they were asked whether the conditions had debuted before, during or after the 1991 GW.

Check-list-based diagnosis

PTSD was formally assessed by the PTSD Checklist-Military Version (PCL-M) [34]. Respondents were asked about symptoms experienced in the month before the interview. Responses were provided on a Likert-type scale, typically ranging from 1 (symptom not experienced) to 5 (extremely bothered). The severity score for each item is summed up and a total PTSD severity score, ranging from a low of 17 to a high of 85 was calculated. A previously established cutoff score of 50 or higher was used to categorize PTSD [34]. The questionnaire also contained scales for assessing depression, panic and anxiety symptoms (PRIME-MD, 35). The Medical Outcomes Study Short Form-36 (SF-36) was used to assess functional status and health-related quality of life [36].

The study was approved by the Human Investigative Committees at Basrah University and Wayne State University as a collaborative research investigation. The study received formal approval from Wayne State University following the removal of former President of Iraq, Saddam Hussein.

Statistical Analyses

The proportions of soldiers and civilians (no civilians in zone₁, which denotes Kuwait) in each zone were calculated. Means and standard deviations for continuous variables are reported. Chi-square tests were used to determine differences between groups. Yates's correction for chi-square tests was used

as indicated by the data. We calculated unadjusted odds ratios (ORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) to determine the univariate associations between military status and self-reported as well as instrument-based and algorithm-based mental health diagnosis. We also calculated adjusted ORs for these associations controlling for age, smoking, and education based on unconditional logistic regression modeling. Age and education were included as continuous variables. We examined associations between distance from Kuwait and mental health. Specifically, we compared zone₁ to zone₃ and zone₂ to zone₃ where zone₃ served as the reference group. We related our distance-based zone-exposure classification scheme to self-reported aggregate war-trauma exposure scores. All reported p-values are 2-tailed and p-values <.05 were considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed using SAS (version 9.1.2, SAS Institute, Cary, NC).

Results

Of the total study group of 1155, 64% (n=742) were deployed soldiers. Among the soldiers, 22.6% had been deployed to zone₁, the Kuwait war zone, 34.1% to zone₂, and 43.4% to zone₃, the reference zone. Among the 413 civilians, 35.6% had resided in zone₂ and 64.4% in zone₃ during the GW.

Table 1 depicts demographics for soldiers and civilians. Soldiers were significantly older, had fewer years of formal schooling, and worse self-reported health as compared to civilians (p<.01). There were no significant differences in smoking history between soldiers and civilians.

Table 1. Demographics and self-reported mental status comparing soldiers to civilians.

Characteristic	All Participants (n= 1155) N (%)	Group		
		Soldiers (n=742) N (%)	Civilians (n=413) N (%)	P*
Age, mean (SD), years	31.0(7.5)	32.1(8.0)	28.7(5.6)	<.001
Body Mass Index / mean (SD)	20.8(2.6)	20.9(2.7)	20.7(2.4)	n.s.
Education Status				<.001
8th Grade or Less	285(25.3)	212(29.2)	73(18.3)	
> 8th Grade but < HS	368(32.7)	218(30.1)	150(37.5)	
Completed HS	252(22.4)	161(22.2)	91(22.8)	
Less than College	48(4.3)	28(3.9)	20(5.0)	
Completed Bachelors or more	172(15.3)	106(14.6)	66(16.5)	
Smoking Status				n.s.
Never smoked	549(48.3)	344(47.3)	205(50.1)	
Former smoker	177(15.6)	115(15.8)	62(15.2)	
Current smoker	410(36.1)	268(36.9)	142(34.7)	
Self-Rated Health Status at Time of Survey				<.01
Excellent	48(4.2)	32(4.3)	16(3.9)	
Very good	231(20.1)	131(17.7)	100(24.5)	
Good	723(63.0)	465(62.8)	258(63.2)	
Fair	125(10.9)	98(13.2)	27(6.6)	
Poor	21(1.8)	14(1.9)	7(1.7)	
Depression	69 (6.1)	60(8.4)	09(2.20)	<.001 [†]
Anxiety	30 (2.7)	26(3.8)	04(1.00)	<.01 [†]

* Data are presented in percentages unless otherwise indicated. Percentages are based on non-missing data.

P* represents the p-value for overall χ^2 tests.

[†] Odds ratios (95% Confidence Intervals), Depression = 4.9 (2.2-11.18) and Anxiety = 3.9 (1.26-13.3) where civilians serve as the reference group.

n.s. = statistically non-significant.

Soldiers reported significantly more often having received a diagnosis of depression during the last year (OR 4.9; 95% confidence interval, CI, 2.2-11.1) and anxiety (OR 3.9; 95% CI, 1.2-13.3) as compared to civilians

Self-reported mental health

Table 2 depicts odds ratios for reporting currently suffering from depression or during the last year, after adjusting for

age, smoking status, and years of education. Participants that were stationed closest to Kuwait had an increased odds ratio reporting suffering from depression as compared to those that had resided in further away located zones. These findings held true for all participants as well as when the analysis was restricted to soldiers only. Anxiety differed only when the war epicenter zone was compared to those that resided 200-300 kilometers from Kuwait.

Mental health assessment using validated scales

We also employed validated scales, not self-reports, for the diagnosis of PTSD, depression, and panic disorders. There were no significant differences between soldiers and civilians in the prevalence of these disorders (Table 3). However, the numbers of depression symptoms were significantly higher among soldiers as compared to civilians.

War trauma exposure by zone

War trauma exposure scores of soldiers only across different war zones; Zone₁ Mean = 38.7/of max 71 (S.E. 4.6), Zone₂, Mean = 49.7 (S.E. 4.6), and Zone₃ Mean = 13.7 (9.7) ($F_2 = 15, 2, p < .01$). Tukey post-hoc tests revealed a significant difference between Zone₂ and any of the other two zones.

Mental health across war zones for soldiers only

Restricting the analysis to soldiers only, we found significant differences across zones for depression, dysthymia, and panic disorders. The number of sub-syndromal scores on the PTSD scale also differed significantly across zones, with the highest number among soldiers having been deployed in the war epicenter. However, no one of the

participants reached the necessary cut-off points for the PTSD diagnosis.

Discussion

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first epidemiological study of mental health among Iraqi soldiers that were actively involved in the 1991 Gulf War. We found a dose-response relationship between geographical closeness to Kuwait and mental health disorders. Self-reported war-related trauma exposure also varies across zones, and reported to be the highest in the southwestern part of Iraq, objectively the center for the Allied forces activities following the liberation of Kuwait.

There have been a substantial number of studies during the last fifteen years concerning the health among veterans of the 1991 Gulf War [1-13]. More recent ones cover, as is the case for the current study, the entire first decade following the completion of the war [27]. Compared to other recent conflicts, for example the 2003 Iraq war and the war in Afghanistan, the GW appears to have resulted in a higher prevalence of medical symptoms and with longer duration [23]. Despite much research, there is no consensus as to the underlying reason behind the elevated

<u>All Participants</u>								
Self-Reported Mental Disorders	All Zones (n=1155)	Zone1 (n=168)	Zone2 (n=400)	Zone3 (n=587)	p*	p ^{Trend}	Odds Ratios (95% Confidence Intervals)	
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)			(Zone 1 vs 2) [†]	(Zone 1 vs 3)
Depression	69(6.1)	46(31.9)	18(4.6)	5(0.9)	<.0001	<.0001	7.6 (2.77-21.79) ⁴	135.6 (43.8-419.8) ⁴
Anxiety	30(2.7)	13(10.9)	7(1.8)	10(1.7)	<.0001	<.0001	0.9 (0.39- 2.9) ¹	5.7 (2.2-14.4) ²
<u>Gulf War Soldiers Only</u>	All Zones (n=742)	Zone1 (n=168)	Zone2 (n=253)	Zone3 (n=321)				
Depression	60(8.4)	46(31.9)	11(4.4)	3(0.9)	<.0001	<.0001	6.6 (1.7-24.9) ²	104.6 (28.0-390.8) ³
Anxiety	26(3.8)	13(10.9)	5(2.0)	8(2.5)	<.0001	<.0001	0.7 (0.20- 2.55) ¹	4.1(1.5- 11.1) ²

Table 2. Self-reported medical history by zone and Odds Ratios (95% Confidence Intervals) for zones 1 vs. 2 and zones 1 vs. 3.

Percentages are based on non-missing data.

Zone 1 = In Kuwait; Zone 2 = 100-199 kilometers from Kuwait; and Zone3 = 200-300 kilometers from Kuwait.

*Represents the p-value for overall χ^2 test.

p^{Trend} represents the p-value for the Cochran-Armitage trend test.

[†]OR represents the magnitude of association between self-reported depression and zone where zone 2 is the reference zone after controlling for age, smoking, and education.

[‡]OR represents the magnitude of association between self-reported anxiety and zone where zone 3 is the reference zone after controlling for age, smoking, and education.

¹ No significant difference; ² $p < 0.01$; ³ $p < 0.001$; ⁴ $p < 0.0001$

prevalence of psychological symptoms in GW veterans as compared to soldiers not deployed to the Gulf in 1991. The mechanism causing PTSD following trauma-exposure is also far from being understood. For example, only a minority of trauma-exposed develop PTSD as compared to depression and anxiety which are more common. However, apart from risk factors such as prior trauma history, female gender, and low intelligence, peri-traumatic psychophysiological arousal and sustained sympathetic arousal have been reported to be reliable predictors of the future development of PTSD [37-38]. Studies of deployed soldiers have reported that depression is a risk factor for the later development of PTSD [40]. Sustained stress exposure increases the risk to develop depression as well as anxiety

[40] PTSD symptoms, in contrast, might not emerge until after removal from a chronic stressor conditions which might partly explain why PTSD symptoms tend to increase with time [40-42]. Prior studies of Allied soldiers have been done when they have already returned to their home country. The Iraqis taken part in the current study are possibly still living under highly stressful conditions, possibly not allowing for the expression of PTSD symptoms. Further support for this idea is the fact that Iraqi refugees, including soldiers, surveyed by us in Michigan, using the same validated instrument exhibit a high rate of PTSD [43]. Studies to date have mostly dealt with members of the Allied forces. Epidemiological studies typically

compare soldiers that have been deployed to the Gulf in 1991 as

Mental Disorder	All Participants (n= 1155) N (%)	Group		
		Soldiers (n=742) N (%)	Civilians (n=413) N (%)	<i>P</i>
PSTD* (%)	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
Number of PTSD symptoms. Mean (SD)	19.1(4.2)	19.1(4.6)	19.0(3.3)	n.s.
Depression**				
No depression	792 (68.6)	494 (66.6)	298 (72.2)	n.s.
Minor depression	326 (28.2)	225 (30.3)	101 (24.5)	
Major depression	37 (3.2)	23 (3.1)	14 (3.4)	
Number of Depression symptoms. Mean (SD)	1.1(1.5)	1.2(1.5)	1.0(1.4)	<.05
Dysthymia	15(1.3)	11(1.5)	4(1.0)	n.s.
Panic Disorder	60(5.2)	45(6.1)	15(3.6)	0.074

Table 3. Mental disorders diagnosed using a validated instrument comparing soldiers with civilians

PTSD, post-traumatic stress disorder; SD, standard deviation; N/A, non-applicable

* PTSD as defined by the Checklist-Military Version (Weathers et al., 1993)

** Depression as defined by the Primary Care Evaluation of Mental Disorders (Spitzer et al., 1996).

n.s. = statistically non-significant.

compared to non-deployed soldiers, or soldiers deployed elsewhere. However, these studies are characterized by a number of important limitations. Typically, deployed soldiers are younger, less educated, of lower socioeconomic status and military rank, and more often single [18, 28]. Allied soldiers deployed to Iraq experienced a number of potentially stressful exposures, apart from GW-specific factors, including being away from familiar territory, the desert climate, sand flies and an environment with different microbial composition from their natural habitat. More recent studies

have linked such “low-intensity” but more chronic stressors, along with stress related to poor morale and administrative hazards to the risk to develop PTSD [40-43]. There is also no financial compensation scheme available to Iraqi soldiers as compared to Allied forces from, for example, the US and UK. All of these factors might be of relevance in identifying reasons for the increased reported rates of medical and mental symptoms in GW veterans since these variables differ systematically and non-randomly between GW veterans and non-deployed referents.

Mental Disorder	Zone1 (n=168) N (%)	Zone2 (n=400) N (%)	Zone3 (n=587) N (%)	P
PSTD*	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
Number of PTSD symptoms, mean (SD)	17.6(5.8)	18.4(3.8)	19.9(3.7)	<.0001
Depression**				
No depression	111 (66.1)	332 (83.0)	349 (59.5)	<.0001
Minor depression	49 (29.2)	59 (14.8)	218 (37.1)	
Major depression	8 (4.8)	9 (2.3)	20 (3.4)	
Number of Depression symptoms, mean (SD)	1.3(1.8)	0.8(1.4)	1.4(1.5)	<.0001
Dysthymia	6(3.6)	9(2.3)	0(0.0)	<.001
Panic Disorder	12(7.1)	12(3.0)	36(6.13)	<.05

Table 4. Mental health disorder diagnosed using a validated instrument by zones ^{1,2,3}

Percentages are based on non-missing data.

Zone 1 = In Kuwait; Zone 2 = 100-199 kilometers from Kuwait; and Zone3 = 200-300 kilometers from Kuwait.

*Represents the p-value for ANOVA test.

** Represents the p-value for overall χ^2 tests.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first epidemiological study of the health of Iraqi soldiers being part of the GW operations in 1991. Moreover, we have assessed Iraqi civilians and have applied a theoretical dose-response model, based on the distance from Kuwait. The theoretical dose-response model is based on the a priori assumption that:

1: soldiers, as compared to civilians, controlling for distance from Kuwait, were hypothesized to have been more exposed to environmental agents, including biological and chemical warfare agents, oil fire smoke, as well as trauma.

2: soldiers closer to Kuwait were also hypothesized to exhibit higher

cumulative harmful war-related exposures as compared to soldiers further away from Kuwait. The highest self-reported war-related exposure was predicted to be in the southwest of Iraq, where the largest chemical weapon storage and destruction took place, including aerial bombing by the Allied forces.

The odds ratios for depression and anxiety were elevated for soldiers as compared to civilians. This held true even after adjusting for possible confounders such as age, smoking status, and years of education. A number of studies of Allied forces also report an increased prevalence of mental disorders, including depression and

anxiety, and chronic fatigue syndrome among GW deployed versus non deployed soldiers [1, 11, 19, 24].

Our study confirms prior findings of GW veterans that mental disorders including depression and anxiety, appear to be the most systematically increased mental health disorders [1, 8, 18, 21, 28].

With regard to our *a priori* hypothesis of a dose-response relationship between the risks for mental health disorders and closeness to the Kuwait, we could not reject it with regard to depression. However, the risk for anxiety was increased for those having resided in either of the two zones closest to Kuwait. We do not believe our dose-response findings are spurious findings since it held true in civilians and soldiers alike. In reality, most of the fighting occurred in the first two zones, that is, within 200 kilometers from Kuwait. Environmental and war-specific exposures, including oil well smoke and aerial bombings were also most frequent in this area. We therefore concur with the suggestion by Wessely et al [44] that one needs to take a broader view of hazards, including exposures to vaccines, smoke from oil fires, and mental stressors. The total exposures to such real or perceived hazards make up the cumulative burden of stress perceived by GW veterans, rather than merely more specific environmental agents. Self-reported war trauma exposure varied significantly across war zones, suggesting that self-reports might be a relevant proxy for distance from Kuwait. Self-reports reflect the fact that the highest war intensities following the collapse of the former Iraqi regime were in the southwestern part of Iraq.

An important difference from prior mental health studies of Allied soldiers deployed to Iraq is that none of our sample, despite the fact that we used a

translated, validated and sensitive scale, met the criteria for PTSD. We do not believe this finding is spurious and due to systematic selection bias. Moreover, in analogy with prior studies of Allied soldiers, we did find an increased risk for depression and anxiety disorders among soldiers.

As reported in many studies of Allied forces, soldiers included in our sample, were less educated and had lower income [18, 24]. However, in contrast to many studies of Allied forces, soldiers in our sample were older [18, 28]. There were no differences in smoking habits between deployed soldiers and civilian controls. Overall, we believe our sample is representative for Iraqi soldiers and civilians in the areas studied.

There are some limitations to the current study. First, we were not able to sample a representative sample of soldiers and civilians. Rather, we selected people that accompanied patients to health clinics that offer care for free. There might have been a systematic bias in our selection. We controlled known confounders, including education and age in our logistic regressions. We also carried out the survey 10 years after the completion of the war. It is possible that we would have gotten different results, should we have surveyed participants closer to the war. However, this was not possible due to lack of access and trust among potential participants during the prior regime. Our self-reported war trauma exposure scale attempted to assess participants' exposure to trauma considered to be of relevance in trauma research. The focus is on conditions where a person's own life was at risk or perceived being threatened. There might be other factors of relevance with regard to the future development of trauma-related mental health disorders. Finally, we used a geographical basis for the

creation of three zones, based on how far away from Kuwait participants resided during the war. These zones coincide well with more objective measures of war activities, with the second zone purportedly having the highest war intensity.

In conclusion, the current study of Iraqi GW veterans as well as civilians confirms many of the prior findings from Allied GW veterans. Moreover, Iraqi soldiers exhibited significantly more mental disorders than did civilians. Closeness to Kuwait was an independent risk factor for mental disorders. Since our sample is used to Iraq, its climate and culture and microbial characteristics, many of the confounders from prior epidemiological studies of Allied GW veterans can be eliminated as possible precipitators of GW-related symptoms and syndromes.

The study also provides new insights as to possible mental health effects from sustained exposure to socio-environmental stressors of relevance for further revisions of evidence-based models of post-trauma adjustment disorders.

Neither soldiers nor civilians residing in Iraq scored above the predetermined cut-off score on the PTSD scale. We believe the scale is culturally valid, since the same scale has been used repeatedly in Iraqi refugees that have relocated to the US finding a high prevalence of PTSD [31, 32]. We believe that as long as the participants are still living under highly stressful conditions, PTSD-like symptoms might be suppressed as part of an overall psycho-physiological coping mechanism [45]. Once a person is removed from highly stressful conditions that elicit the “fight-or-flight response”, there is a drastic rebound effect, possible contributing to eliciting PTSD-like symptoms. Our findings point to the

importance of studying where in the relocation process, PTSD symptoms are being expressed. Such an understanding might contribute to our efforts in preventing and treating PTSD.

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Bengt B. Arnetz participated in the design of the analysis, guided the statistical analysis, participated in interpreting statistical results, and was chief author of the manuscript.

Thamer A. Hamdan was the study supervisor in Iraq. He was responsible for training the medical interviewers, securing access to clinics where interviews with participants were done. He contributed to the analytical process and writing the manuscript.

Sawsan W. Shukri reviewed data entry for correctness and translated entered data, when necessary, from Arabic to English. She also contributed to writing the manuscript.

Mary Grzybowski was in charge of the statistical analysis. She also contributed to the analytical design, interpretation of statistical results, and in writing the manuscript.

Richard Severson contributed to discussions regarding the analytical approach and commented on prior manuscript drafts.

Hikmet Jamil established the collaboration between Wayne State University and Basrah University in Iraq to conduct this research. He contributed to methods and analytical design, interpretation of statistical results, and in writing the manuscript.

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Letter A incision periareolar mastopexy with breast implant augmentation

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Abstract

20 females with mild to moderate drooping of breasts, undergone mastopexy and augmentation of breast at the same time, through letter A (upper half of areola) periareolar incision, after pointing the position of new areola towards the narrow part of letter A. We excised the excess skin, inserted the breast implant (silicon, saline filled) according to the size that the patients selected, closed the skin in layers. High satisfaction rate about 80% was achieved with very small post operative scars and few complications. The aim of this paper is to report our surgical experience in performing one-stage mastopexy with breast augmentation, with small periarolar scar, in 20 patients with mild to moderate drooping of the breasts.

Keywords: Mastopexy, Breast implant, letter A incision

Introduction

The breast is the most important organ in the female's bodies, so any deformity to the breasts will affect their femininity. So there are many procedures to improve the shape of the breasts and correct any deformity.

Vertical mammoplasty is an effective alternative to inverted-T methods.

Among other benefits, it results in a significantly reduced scar pattern. There exists a subset of patients with ptosis who are candidates for a scar pattern that is further reduced [1].

A technique of mastopexy has been outlined that is extremely versatile for restoring an aesthetic and youthful breast shape in the patient who has lost a massive amount of weight [2]. Mastopexy is virtually always required in the female massive weight loss patient, and breast augmentation is often an important adjunct to breast-lifting procedures [3].

One-stage mastopexy with breast augmentation is an increasingly popular procedure, although some recommend a staged mastopexy and breast augmentation [4].

The inverted-T incision for mastopexy of saggy breast continues to be associated with the three most common complications for this technique; suture spitting, excess scarring, and bottoming out [5]. With time, the augmented breast frequently becomes ptotic and patients may return requesting mastopexy. Experience has shown that secondary mastopexy in the augmented breast is fraught with potential complications,

including fat necrosis, skin flap loss, and nipple ischemia.

The long-term presence of implants typically results in changes in breast anatomy and physiology, including parenchymal atrophy, tissue thinning, and diminished skin blood supply. These factors greatly increase the surgical risks of secondary mastopexy [6].

Primary augmentation/mastopexy is a commonly performed procedure and has a significantly less complication rate than secondary augmentation/mastopexy which is also common and has higher revision and complication rates [7].

In one study the most common complications after breast surgery were hematomas, present in 46 patients (1.5%), infections in 33 patients (1.1%), and breast asymmetries in 23 patients (0.8%), rippling in 21 patients (0.7%), and capsular contractures in 14 patients (0.5%) [8].

Problems with circumareolar mastopexy procedures include areola spreading, hypertrophic scar, and recurrence of the ptosis largely because of tension on the closure. To minimize this tension associated with a conventional crescent mastopexy procedure, by excising parenchyma with the crescent of skin as well as two small triangles of parenchyma on either side of the areola. Implant augmentation was performed at the same time. The described operation is indicated for patients who have a small to moderate amount of ptosis. The best candidate is the patient whose areola-inframammary distance is not excessive. Nine such patients received this "extended crescent mastopexy with augmentation" and were followed for up to 3 years. Areola spreading and

hypertrophic scar were kept to a minimum. Although not the final answer for ptosis patients, the extended crescent mastopexy with augmentation has been a step in the right direction [9].

The image of the breast is a symbol of femininity and plays an essential role in the way a woman looks at herself and contributes to her personal and social development. Fashion nowadays uncovers rather than covers a woman's body, and long scars resulting from mammoplasty are less accepted now than they were in the past, more so because the scar quality is unforeseeable. The main concern of mastopexy is to limit the scars, creating a nice breast shape. Ideally scarring is confined to the periareolar circle [10].

Mastopexy and augmentation together can be a very difficult combination of procedures to perform. In many cases, the position of the implant can be inappropriate, necessitating reoperation[11]. Periareolar mastopexy with mammary implants in treatment of ptosis (NAC). This technique does not allow great elevation of the areola (no more than 4-5 cm), but it is good and safe for correcting minor to moderate ptosis combined with volume augmentation[12]. The aim of this paper is to report our surgical experience in performing one-stage mastopexy with breast augmentation, with small periarolar scar, in 20 patients with mild to moderate drooping of the breasts.

Patients and Methods

20 female patients with small to medium size breasts with moderate drooping of areolar-nipple complex (ANC) one stage mastopexy

augmentation of their breasts. Their age ranged from 29-45 years. 14 patients (70%) have moderate drooping of the breasts and 6 patients (30%) have mild drooping of the breasts.

We prepared the patients and took photographs, then we draw letter A in upper half of ANC, the position of new (ANC) will be in the direction of the narrow part of letter A, then we incise

the skin deepithelialized, the triangle of letter A. The breast implant inserted through the periareolar line of letter A, to sub glandular area, the parenchymal breast tissue and the skin sutured in layer followed by the application of a local antibiotic, and frequent dressing. The patients were followed up for 2 years without recurrence.

Results

The numbers of the patients have drooping of the breast increased with the increase of the age as shown in table [1]. 13 patients (65%) have very good the post-operative scar results after 8 months from surgery.

AGE GROUPS	
5 patients	29-33 years
3 patients	34-38 years
4 patients	39-42 years
8 patients	43-45 years

Table (1): The numbers of the patients and their age groups

5 patients (25%) have well the post-operative scar results after 8 months from surgery, and 2 patients (10%) have poor the post-operative scar results after 8 months from surgery. Only 3 patients

developed complications; small hematoma, wound dehescence, and infections.

16 (80%) patients were highly satisfied with the surgical results, 2 (10%) patients were satisfied with surgical results, and 2 (10%) patients were not satisfied with surgical results.

Discussion

The female when grow older, become more concerned with the shape of their breasts. The aging process have great role in the sagging of the breast, also hormonal changes that affect the breast paranchymal, glandular tissue, so breast become laxly and redundant [13].

The different techniques were evaluated with regard to patient selection, operative techniques, scar length, and complications .Plastic surgeons should weigh the advantages and limitations of each technique to correctly address breast ptosis [14].The determining variables in the selection are ptosis of the nipple-areola complex (NAC) and distance from the NAC to the inframammary fold , in using the periareolar pexy for correction of ptosis, the degree of general satisfaction with this technique was 82% [15].

In this study the surgical results and satisfaction rate of 80% are comparable to other studied [16, 17, 18].The main limitation of this report is the small sample of patients.

Conclusion: According to our modest experience on this small sample of patients, we think it is possible to perform the combined procedure of mastopexy and implantation, to minimize the complications, and to

obtain satisfactory results over the mid and long terms

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The prevalence of hepatitis B and C serological markers among patients with thalassaemia in Mosul

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Abstract

Background: Thalassaemic patients are known to have higher risk of developing hepatitis B and C than normal individuals. The aim of this paper is to study the prevalence of hepatitis B and C among thalassaemic patients in the province of Mosul.

Patients and methods: From August 2003 to March 2004, 626 patients under the age of 20 years with thalassaemia were surveyed and screened for hepatitis HBs Ag and anti-HC Antibody (Ab) in the Thalassaemia Center in Ibn AL-Atheer Children Hospital in Mosul.

Results: 5.59% of the patients have positive HBs Ag (1.92% of them have combined hepatitis B and C), 28.12% have anti-HC Ab. The prevalence of hepatitis B and C was higher in patients over 15 years.

Conclusion: Viral hepatitis is prevalent in thalassaemic patients in Mosul. Seropositivity is significantly related to age, vaccination, family history of hepatitis, history of splenectomy; number of blood transfusion per year, and severity of thalassaemia.

Keywords: Thalassaemia, HBs Ag, HCV, Serologic markers-Prevalence

Introduction

B-thalassaemia constitutes one of the most serious health problems worldwide, accounting for a major number of childhood deaths per year primarily in regions of the world endemic for malaria.

Viral hepatitis continues to be a major health problem in developed and developing countries. The hepatitis B virus is globally distributed among humans. HBV alone is estimated to have infected 400 million people throughout the globe, making HBV one of the most common human pathogens. [1, 2]

HCV is now recognized as the cause of almost all of the parentally acquired cases of what was previously known as non-A, non-B hepatitis. [3]. The virus is transmitted primarily by blood and blood products in the majority of infected individuals have either received blood transfusions prior to 1990 or have used intravenous drugs. [4]

Little data are available on the seroprevalence of, and risk factors for hepatitis B and C viruses (HBV and HCV) infection in thalassaemic patients in Mosul.

The aim of this paper is to study the prevalence of hepatitis B and C in the thalassaemic patients under the age of 20 in the province of Mosul.

Patients and Methods

This study was carried out in the Thalassaemic Center in Ibin Al- Atheer Children Hospital in Mosul during the period from August 2003 to March 2004. The medical records of 626 patients with thalassaemia were surveyed and analyzed. All the patients included have screening for hepatitis HBs Ag and anti-HC Antibody (Ab). The following data were collected from each medical record:

1. Name, age and sex.
2. Residence, family history of hepatitis and past surgical history.
3. Vaccination history whether complete or incomplete.
4. Frequency of blood transfusion per year (monthly or more than once per month).
5. Duration of disease (B-thalassaemia) and type of thalassaemia.
6. Serological viral markers were screened second generation ELISA test for anti-HCV Ab and by ELISA test for HBs Ag which were done once for each patient.

The results were analyzed using the Chi-squared distribute (X²) and degree of freedom (DF) to obtain the p-value.

Results

The prevalence of anti-hepatitis C Ab and HBs Ag in thalassaemic patients are significantly high. 5.59% of the patients had positive HBs Ag. 1.92% have

combined hepatitis B and C, 28.12% have anti HC-Ab. The prevalence of hepatitis B and C was higher among older age group (older than 15 years). P-value <0.0001.

Seropositivity is significantly related to age, vaccination, family history of hepatitis, history of splenectomy, frequency of blood transfusion per year; and severity of thalassaemia.

The sex has no significance in the prevalence of hepatitis B and C in thalassaemic child. The prevalence of hepatitis B and C did not significantly differ between urban and rural areas. The residence was not risk factor for hepatitis [p-value =0.193 (>0.05)].

Vaccination against hepatitis B was a crucial factor that affects the rate of prevalence of hepatitis; 11.26% of the patient were not vaccinated and only 0.37% of the patients vaccinated (p-value <0.0001).

Thalassaemic patients with splenectomy have higher rate of hepatitis B and C prevalence (52.74%) in comparison with those without splenectomy (19.02%) (P-value<0.0001)

There was clear and evident relationship between the frequency of transfusion and prevalence of hepatitis B and C. with more than 12 blood transfusion per year. 42.02% are hepatitis positive while only (20.67%) with less than 12 per year were positive

The type (severity) of thalassaemic has strong relation with the prevalence of hepatitis Band C, p-value (<0.0001)

With disease duration for more than 6 year (i.e. before screening program application) 46.31% of them where hepatitis positive and the disease for less than 6 years (i.e. after screening program application) 14.63% of them where hepatitis B positive.

The total number surveyed was 626 ; 164 (26.20%) of them were hepatitis C positive ,23 patients (3.67%) were hepatitis B positive and 12 patients (1.92%) had both hepatitis B and C. as shown in the table.1 below: Anti-HC Ab were positive in 164 patients (26.20%).

There is direct relationship between the age and the seropositivity to anti-HCV Ab and HBs Ag. Chi-square=92.654, P-value<0.000,DF =3 (very highly significant)where 69.56% of the hepatitis positive patients where older than 15 years (10.87% for hepatitis B,50% for hepatitis C and 8.69% for co-infection with hepatitis B and C) while only 14.04% of the patients younger than 6 year. There is no significant relation between sex and the prevalence of hepatitis Band C where the P-value=0.441(>0.05). Chi-square=0.595, p-value=0.44(>0.05), DF =1(not significant).

There is no relation between the residence and the prevalence of hepatitis Band C, where p-value=0.193(>0.05) Chi-square=1.692, p value=0.193.17(>0.05), DF=1(not significant).

The interfamilial transmission of hepatitis B and C in thalassaemic patients was highly significant; where 62.37% of the patient had positive family history of hepatitis while only 18.86% had negative family history of hepatitis. Chi-square=114.098, p-value<0.0001, DF=1 (very highly significant)

	Hepatitis B Number	Hepatitis C Number	Hepatitis B and C Number
Age(year)	No.	No.	No.
0-5	5	27	1
6-10	6	47	3
11-15	7	67	4
16-20	5	23	4
Total	23	164	12
Sex			
Male	11	90	9
Female	12	74	3
Total	23	164	12
Residence			
Urban	10	75	5
Rural	13	89	7
Total	23	164	12
Family history positive			
Family history positive	13	93	10
Family history positive	10	71	2
Hepatitis B Vaccination status			
Positive	1		
Negative	17		
Incomplete	17		
Splenectomized patient	14	102	9
Non-splenectomized patient	9	62	3
Thalassemia type			
Major	23	160	12
Intermediate	0	4	0
Transfusion frequency			
<12 year	6	53	3
>12year	17	111	9
Disease duration			
0-5 year	6	35	1
>6 year	17	129	11

Table (1): Results summary

There is highly significant relation between vaccination and the prevalence of hepatitis B seropositivity, hepatitis B was positive in 11.26% of those patient who were not vaccinated while only 0.37% of thalassaemic patients were completely vaccinated regime. Chi-square=25.835, p-value<0.0001, DF=2 (highly significant)

There is highly significant relation between splenectomy and the prevalence of hepatitis B and C, where 52.74% of splenectomized patient had positive hepatitis (5.91% with hepatitis B, 43.03% with hepatitis C and 3.8% with co-infection) while only 19.02% of the non-splenectomized patient were hepatitis positive. Chi-square=77.224, p-value<0.0001, d.f=1 (very highly significant)

There is highly significant association between the type (severity) of thalassaemia and the seropositivity of hepatitis B and C. Where the prevalence of hepatitis was high in thalassaemia major (23.92%) while only (6.25%) in thalassaemia intermedia had hepatitis. Chi-square=21.444, p value<0.0001, DF=1 (very highly significant)

The seropositivity for hepatitis B and C is significantly related to the frequency of blood transfusion per a year, where 20.67% of the hepatitis positive patients received 12 or less transfusion per a year (2% for hepatitis B, 17.67% for hepatitis C and 1% for co-infection) while 42.02% of the hepatitis positive patient received more than 12 transfusion per a year (5.21% with hepatitis B, 34.05% with hepatitis C and 2.77% for co-infection), Chi-square=32.866, p-value<0.0001, DF=1 (very highly significant)

There is highly significant relation between the prevalence of hepatitis B and

C and the duration of the disease, where 46.31% of the patients whose disease duration more than 6 year (5.01% with hepatitis B, 38.05% with hepatitis C and 3.24% with co-infection) while only 14.63% of the patient with the disease less than 6 year. Chi-square=71.929, p-value<0.0001, DF=1 (very highly significant).

Discussion

The prevalence of hepatitis B and C was higher in patients older than 15 years in Mosul and also in Taiwan [5]. The residence was not a risk factor for hepatitis in Mosul and also in Egypt [6].

Vaccination against hepatitis B was crucial factor that affect the prevalence of Hepatitis and this has been shown previously [7]. Family history was a significant risk factor (p-value<0.0001) this has also been shown previously [7, 8, 9]. The positive relationship between the severities of thalassaemia, the duration of the disease and frequency of transfusion and prevalence of hepatitis B and C was shown in this study and previous studies [5, 10, 11, 12].

Conclusion: Seropositivity is significantly related to age, vaccination, family history of hepatitis, history of splenectomy, number of blood transfusion per year; and severity of thalassaemia.

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Effectiveness of zinc protoporphyrin and hemoglobin concentrations in identifying iron deficiency in a group of fewer than five children

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Abstract

Background: Iron deficiency anemia is known to impair cognitive and psychomotor development. Hemoglobin and zinc protoporphyrin (ZPP) tests are commonly used to screen for iron deficiency. However, little research has been done to systematically evaluate the sensitivity and specificity of these 2 tests.

Objective: The aim of this study is evaluating the effectiveness of ZPP test in Identifying iron deficiency anemia in under five-year old children.

Methods: These studies were approved by Nutrition Research Institute, ministry of health. The subjects, 195 children (62 % males and 38 % females), were seen in pediatric clinic during the period from April 2006 to April 2007. The children were all between 1 and 5 years of age. Iron status of the subjects was evaluated as a routine part of patient care at the clinic. Whole blood hemoglobin concentration, hematocrit ratio, and the ZPP/H (Heme) ratio were measured. The ZPP/H ratio was then evaluated as a single indicator of iron status. Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid-

anticoagulant blood had been obtained used to perform the ZPP/H test.

Results: The mean Hemoglobin concentration for the study sample size (195) was (9.9 mg/dl) and Hb test was used as the reference test to compare the effectiveness of ZPP in detecting Iron deficiency anemia, with a sensitivity of (80.6 %) and a specificity of (93.1 %), positive predictive value (93.5 %), negative predictive value (79.4 %), the ZPP appears to be an excellent test in detecting anemia.

Conclusion: ZPP/H ratio measurement alone can detect iron anemic deficiency better than other individual tests. Because the ZPP/H ratio is a functional indicator of long-term iron status, it is an attractive screen test for deficiency. The ZPP/H ratio is a cost-effective test that is performed using as little as one drop of capillary blood.

Keywords: Iron deficiency anemia, Protoporphyrin (ZPP) tests, Children

Introduction

Although iron deficiency is decreasing in industrialized societies, it is still the most common childhood nutritional deficiency [1]. In the United States, the prevalence of childhood iron deficiency with or without anemia has been

estimated in different reports over the last 20 years to range from 3% to 44% [2,3] , In young children, iron deficiency with anemia impairs cognitive function and psychomotor development[4,7]. Iron deficits at an early age are of particular concern because some of the sequelae may be irreversible [8, 9], although the question of reversibility remains unresolved [10, 11].

Iron deficiency most often is diagnosed based on either hemoglobin concentration or hematocrit measurement, i.e., after the onset of anemia. In fact, no single biochemical indicator in current routine use is consistently diagnostic of iron deficiency, particularly in the anemic state. Although combining several iron status indicators provide the best assessment [12, 13], multiple testing is impractical for screening purposes and as a single test, the commonly used hematocrit measurement is inadequate.

Normally, a trace of zinc rather than iron is incorporated into protoporphyrin during the final step of hem biosynthesis. In states of iron-deficient erythropoiesis, zinc protoporphyrin (ZPP) formation is enhanced. These interrelated reactions can be summarized as follows:

Although reaction A greatly predominates at all times (normally

~30 000 to 1), a very slight decrease in iron availability, as in beginning iron depletion, causes reaction B to increase with the ZPP binding to globins in maturing erythrocytes. Thus, the zinc protoporphyrin/heme ratio (ZPP/H), which is essentially the ratio of these reaction products, reflects iron status in the bone marrow during hemoglobin formation. As a physiologic or functional measure of iron utilization, ZPP/H correlates well with hemoglobin concentration in states of iron deficiency anemia [15].

Using the simple technique of hematofluorometry to measure the ZPP/H ratio in whole blood, we have studied the effectiveness of this index in screening for iron depletion or for deficiency in children seen for routine examination in a pediatric hospital.

Patients and Methods

These studies were approved by Nutrition Research Institute, Ministry of Health. The subjects, 195 children (girls and boys), were seen in pediatric clinic. The children were all between 1 and 5 years of age and none was under 1 year of age. Iron status of the subjects was evaluated as a routine part of patient care at the clinic. Whole blood hemoglobin concentration, hematocrit ratio, and the ZPP/H ratio were measured. The ZPP/H ratio then was evaluated as a single indicator of iron status.

Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid-anticoagulant blood had been obtained used to perform the ZPP/H test.

Children enrolled in the study were those attending Al-Mansoure Pediatric Hospital during the period from April 2006 to April 2007.

Laboratory

The hematocrit and hemoglobin concentrations were determined. ZPP/H ratio was measured on a ZPP - hematofluorometer (206D) manufactured by Biomedical company in USA. Hematocrit and hemoglobin concentrations both represent the major end-product of iron utilization revealed by the onset of anemia. ZPP/H ratio reflects bone marrow.

The ZPP/H ratio is measured directly using a dedicated instrument called a hematofluorometer. Used without reagent required microscope cover slides. A measure of iron status requires one drop of whole blood, and the result can be obtained in ~1 minute.

Results

The total number of cases collected during the study period from the children specialized hospital is 195 cases, (62 %) of these cases are males and (38 %) are females. Anemic cases confirmed by using serum Hb level as a standard reference test and of the 108 children who were anemic (identified by Hb confirmatory testing); the highest percentage (62 %) of confirmed anemic cases was in males. Both tests were able to identify 87 cases of anemia and 21 cases were identified by Hb test alone while 6 cases of anemia were detected by ZPP test alone, as shown in Figure (1).

The **sensitivity** of ZPP test is the probability that it will produce a true positive result when used on a diseased population (as compared to a reference or "gold standard") while The **specificity** of ZPP test is the probability that it will produce a true negative result when used on a non-diseased population (as

determined by a reference or "gold standard").

Figure (1): The Numbers of iron-deficient children identified with screening tests

A test must be sensitive enough to identify a large proportion of individuals with a given condition while being specific enough to rule out the condition in a large percentage of healthy individuals, the test must be reliable, and early detection of a condition or illness through screening must be associated with patient benefit Hence, confirming the validity (accuracy) of the ZPP test in detecting anemia, a 2 by 2 Contingency table constricted to record and analyses the relationship between the two main variables (confirmed Anemia cases and ZPP test results) ,table (1) , With a sensitivity of (80.6 %) and a specificity of (93.1 %) , the ZPP appears to be an excellent test in detecting anemia as shown in table (2).

The **positive predictive value** will detect proportion of patients with positive test results who are correctly diagnosed and this can be an important indicator in evaluation of screening program effectiveness and with a percentage of (93.5 %) will indicate that

ZPP test is effective in detecting cases which are correctly diagnosed as anemic and with a **negative predictive value** (proportion of patients with negative test results who are correctly diagnosed) of (79.4 %) will make ZPP test able to detect a good proportion of non-anemic patients who are not having the disease making ZPP test a cost-effective test in identifying Iron deficiency anemia, Table(1) and Table (2). No significant difference were found between children with or without anemia with respect to gender with an odds ratio of (0.99) for a 95% confidence Interval between (CI=0.560 – 1.783) as shown in table (3)

		Anemia using Hb test		
		"+"	"-"	Total
ZPP Test	"+"	87	6	93
	"-"	21	81	102
Total		108	87	195

Table (1): a 2 by 2 contingency table showing the number of anemia cases detected using Hb test and ZPP test

	Sensitivity	Specificity	Positive Predictive Value	Negative Predictive Value
ZPP test	80.60%	93.10%	93.50%	79.40%

Table (2): Evaluation of ZPP test in detecting anemia regarding its validity and effectiveness

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95 % Confidence Interval (95% CI)
Gender (male vs. Female)	0.99	(0.560 - 1.783)

Table (3): Relative Risk of Anemia among under (five year's) old children in relation to gender (Male vs. Female)

Discussion

Historically, hemoglobin concentration or hematocrit measurements have been used to screen for iron deficiency. In the case of iron status, the laboratory plays a primary role, and we have shown that for children the ZPP/H ratio is useful for assessing iron status. The gold standard that has been used to define iron deficiency is decreased or absent stainable iron in bone marrow aspirate. Clearly, marrow biopsy is not an acceptable alternative for routine assessment of iron status.

The ability of the ZPP/H ratio to detect small changes in overall iron status is indicated clearly by these findings. Because ZPP/H ratio reflects long-term iron status, the ZPP/H ratio is responsive to the early stages of iron depletion. ZPP/H ratio of 80 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ has been assigned as a practical upper limit.

The ZPP/H ratio is considered by some investigators to be a nonspecific test. This is attributable to the many causes that may underlie iron-deficient erythropoiesis, including anemia of chronic disease, chronic infections.

Conclusion:

The ZPP/H ratio measurement alone could detect anemic deficiency better than other individual tests. Because the ZPP/H ratio is a functional indicator of long-term iron status, it is an attractive screen test for deficiency. The ZPP/H ratio is a cost-effective test that is performed using as little as one drop of capillary blood with instrument suitable for use at sites remote from a central laboratory.

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Study in two different procedures for repair of hypospadias

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Abstract

Background: Repair of hypospadias remains one of the challenging problems for pediatric surgeons. The aim of this paper is to compare two commonly used procedures in repairing proximal hypospadias; the perimeatal based flap (Mathieu) procedure, and the tubularized incised plate (Snodgrass) urethroplasty procedure.

Patients and methods: 64 patients who undergone hypospadias repair for distal hypospadias coronal, subcoronal and anterior shaft over a three-year period from January 2005 to December 2007 in pediatric surgery unit \ The Maternity and Child Teaching Hospital Al-Qadisiya –Iraq were reviewed. Patients were assigned into two groups to undergo either Snodgrass or Mathieu surgical repair by a single surgeon. The majority of patients aged 3 to 5 years.

Results: A perimeatal skin flap (Mathieu repair) was performed in 42 (65.6%) patients and tubularized incised plate (TIP) urethroplasty (Snodgrass procedure) in 22 (34.3%) patients. Cosmetic results were excellent with Snodgrass repair with a normal looking slit like meatus.

Conclusion: Combining the Mathieu procedure with plate incision can be

a promising simple technique to achieve a normally shaped meatus and to reduce the rate of meatal-related complications.

Keywords: Repair, Hypospadias, Procedures

Introduction

Hypospadias is one of the most common congenital anomalies occurring in approximately 1:250 to 1:300 live births. Complication in hypospadias surgery has been an important title for the pediatric urologists worldwide. In the United States data from two birth defects surveillance systems has shown an unexplained doubling in the incidence of hypospadias [1]. The aim of surgery in hypospadias is to achieve a functional penis with a normal cosmetic appearance. The commonest repairs to correct distal hypospadias are the Thiersch-Duplay [2], Mathieu [3], Mustarde, meatal advancement and glanuloplasty (MAGPI) and tubularized incised plate (TIP) urethroplasty [4, 5]. Of these procedures Mathieu and TIP urethroplasty (Snodgrass repair) have been widely practiced. Snodgrass being now the preferred method since it creates a vertical slit-like normal appearing meatus, unlike the horizontally oriented and rounded meatus ('Fish mouth')

produced by the meatal based (Mathieu) flap repair. This procedure allows construction of neourethra from the existing urethral plate without additional skin flaps [6, 7].

When the meatus is too proximal on the shaft to perform a MAGPI procedure, or when there is no deep glanular groove appropriate for GAP or in situ tabularization technique, the meatus is advanced onto the glans using the technique described in 1932 by the French surgeon Mathieu [8]. This technique involves the use of a perimeatal skin flap, based on the intrinsic blood supply to ensure viability, the length-to-width ratio of the skin flap not exceeding 2:1. Historically, if the urethral groove was not wide enough for tabularization in situ, an alternative approach was taken, more recently the concept of incising the urethral plate, with subsequent tabularization and secondary healing, was introduced by Snodgrass [9]. The technique is versatile and suitable for almost all distal [10] lesions. Both Mathieu and Snodgrass make use of the urethral plate which makes the appearance to near natural [11].

Patients and Methods

64 patients who have undergone hypospadias repair for distal hypospadias coronal, subcoronal and anterior shaft in a randomized clinical trial over a three-year period from January 2005 to December 2007 in the pediatric surgery unit \ The Maternity and Child Teaching Hospital Al-Qadisiya -Iraq. Patients were assigned into two groups to undergo either Snodgrass or Mathieu surgical repair by a single surgeon. Inclusion criteria were anterior hypospadias and age of 14 years or less (the age of children ranged from

seven months to 14 years with the majority (85%) less than 5 years at the time of surgery). Exclusion criteria were associated chordee, history of circumcision, and surgical repair history. On a random basis, 42 patients undergone surgical repair using Mathieu technique (figure-1, 2) and 22 patients using Snodgrass technique. All surgeries were performed by one single surgeon. All patients were operated on under general anesthesia. A tourniquet was applied and adrenalin 1:200000 used to maintain a bloodless field. A straight penis was confirmed by performing an artificial erection. Surgical instruments, suture materials (5-0 Vicryl) and urinary diversion (Foley 6 F to 8 F) were the same for all patients. For Mathieu flip flap repair a paramental based flap was raised with its intact blood supply and anastomosed with the urethral plate after mobilizing the latter with two parallel incisions.

Figure (1)-: A: Subcoronal hypospadias perimeatal flap (Mathieu).B: (Mathieu) with stent

Figure (2): perimeatal flap (Mathieu) with stent final result

Figure (3): A Tubularized incised plate (Snodgrass), B: A vascularized dartos flap harvested from subcutaneous tissue of dorsal prepuce skin, C: Snodgrass procedure final result with stent

Repair performed in three layers over a stent. Polyglycolic acid (5-0 Vicryl) interrupted sutures were used for repair, keeping the knots inside the urethral lumen in most of our patients.

For Snodgrass repair (Figure-3), a U-shaped incision was made extending along the edges of the urethral plate to healthy skin 2 mm proximal to the meatus. Flaps mobilized for a tension free repair. The urethral plate was then incised in midline from the hypospadiac meatus distally. Incised plate was then tubularized over a 6 F or 7 F stent (folly) using interrupted polyglycolic acid (Vicryl no. 5-0) sutures. Neourethra was then covered with a vascularized dartos flap harvested from subcutaneous tissue of dorsal prepuce skin (pictures, figure 8, 9, 10). All patients were maintained on antibiotic prophylaxis. Stent was removed after 4-6 days. Patients were followed for 3 to 6 months. Data including duration of the surgery, stenting time, duration of hospitalization, and any kind of complications such as break down, meatal stenosis, and fistula formation were collected. Also, success rate was calculated for every single patient. The information related to operation along with findings in follow-ups was recorded in forms and they were compared between the two groups.

Results

A total of 64 cases were studied. Group I (n=42) undergone Mathieu repair and Group II (n=22) undergone Snodgrass repair. Age ranged between 7 months to 14 years with the mean of 4 years. Majority of patients aged 3 to 5 years range. Coronal hypospadias was present in 32 (50 %), subcoronal in 23 (35 %) and distal penile (anterior shaft) in 9 (14).

%) patients. Presurgical hormonal treatment was not given to any of our patients. Mean operative time was 62 ± 15.05 minutes and 77 ± 13.03 minutes in Mathieu and Snodgrass groups, respectively. A perimeatal skin flap (Mathieu repair) was performed in 42 (65.6%) patients and tubularized incised plate (TIP) urethroplasty (Snodgrass procedure) in the rest of 22 (34.3%) patients.

Mean stenting duration was 4.05 ± 1.31 days and 5.01 ± 1.06 days in Mathieu and Snodgrass groups, respectively. Hospital stay was 3.43 ± 1.56 days in Mathieu group and 3.55 ± 1.29 days in Snodgrass group. Statistical analysis showed no differences between the two groups. Wound breakdown was seen in 4.5% (n=4) in each group and urocutaneous fistula in 5 patients 11.5% (n=11) in Mathieu group and 1 patient 4.5% (n=4) in Snodgrass group. This was later on repaired by a local rotational flap. Meatal stenosis was seen in 4.5% (n=4) approximately in each group which was subsequently treated with meatal dilatation and meatotomy.

Proximal urethral stricture was seen in 2 patients 7.1% (n=7) in Mathieu group and in 2 patients 9% (n=9) in Snodgrass group. Stream abnormality was seen only in those having meatal stenosis which improved with meatal dilatation or meatotomy. Wound dehiscence was equal in both the procedures approximately 4.5% (n=4) each (table - 1). Cosmetic results were excellent with Snodgrass repair with a normal looking slit like meatus.

	Snodgrass	Mathieu	P value
Number of patient	22	42	
Mean operative time in minute	77 ± 13.03	62 ± 15.05	0.55
Mean stenting duration (days)	5.01 ± 1.06	4.05 ± 1.31	0.65
Mean Hospital stay (days)	3.55 ± 1.29	3.43 ± 1.56	0.75
Wound breakdown (%)	4.5% (n=4)	4.7% (n=4)	
Meatal stenosis (%)	4.5% (n=4)	4.5% (n=4)	
Proximal urethral stricture (%)	9% (n=2)	7.1% (n=7)	
Wound dehiscence (%)	4.5% (n=4)	2.3% (n=2)	
Urocutaneous (%) fistula	4.5% (n=4)	11.5% (n=11)	

Table-(1): Show the results of two procedures in this study

Discussion

Hypospadias is a congenital anomaly in which meatal orifice opens to anterior part of penis instead of the glans apex, because of a defect in urethral development. Its incidence rate is about 1 in 300 male live births. About 50% to 70% of hypospadias cases are the anterior types. [12, 13]. More than 200 methods of repair have been introduced throughout the 125 years history of hypospadias repair. Earlier most of the distal lesions were repaired with meatal-based flip flap procedure (Mathieu repair). Although this repair produced a glanular meatus, the opening was often rounded, in contrast to the slit like appearance of a normal meatus. This technique was first described by Mathieu in 1932 for distal hypospadias using a meatal based flap [14]. Then in 1981 Wacksman reported his initial experience with this technique [15]. In 1987, Rabinowitz described catheterless repair using the Mathieu repair [16]. Although 1 and 2-layer neourethral anastomoses have demonstrated satisfactory results, the two layer

	Our study	Aminsharifi [25]	Imamoglu [26]	Mahmoudrez [27]	Anwar-ul [28]	Amr [32]	Kajbafzadeh [29]
Mean operative time in minute	62 ± 15.05	100		94	60	165	
Mean stenting duration (days)	4.05± 1.31		7.1 ± 0.67	5.06			4.5
Mean Hospital stay (days)	3.43 ± 1.56		7.5 ± 1.19	3.93	3		4.5
Wound breakdown (%)	4.7 (n=4)			0	1.1	9	0
Meatal stenosis (%)	4.5 (n=4)	0			5.5		0
Proximal urethral stricture (%)	7.1 (n=7)		3.7	0	3.3		
Wound dehiscence (%)	2.3 (n=2)		7.4				0
Urocutaneous (%) fistula	11.5 (n=11)	0	7.4	5.55	7.7	18.6	Nil

Table (2): The results in our study and six studies using Mathieu technique

technique has produced lower complication rates [17].

Careful preservation of the vasculature of the flap and avoidance of overlapping suture lines produce a watertight closure with minimal risk of postoperative fistula formation. Mathieu repair also provides good functional results but a cosmetic is more preserved in Snodgrass repair. Minimal complication rate has been reported even with stentless repair [18]. Even now, Mathieu procedure is considered as the standard procedure by some surgeons, for distal

hypospadias [19, 20, 21]. Rich et al incised the urethral plate in the midline to improve cosmetics of a hypospadias repair in 1989[22]. In 1994, Snodgrass advanced this concept by extending the incision of the urethral plate from the meatus to the tip of the glans [23]. This maneuver allowed construction of a new urethra from the existing urethral plate. It was suggested that healing may occur through re-epithelialization of the relaxing incision without obvious scarring; allowing the incised edges to remain separated [24].

In a study by Aminsharifi et al [25], Mathieu technique results with and without urethral stenting were compared in 40 cases of anterior hypospadias. significant difference was seen in fistula formation (0% vs. 15%) and total surgical complications rate (0% vs. 5%) in Mathieu and Snodgrass techniques respectively. They concluded that combining the Mathieu procedure with plate incision could be considered as a promising simple technique to achieve a normally shaped meatus and to reduce the rate of meatal-related complications, the major concern with the Snodgrass procedure. In the study by Imamoglu M. Abdurrahim et al [26], these two techniques were compared regarding fistula formation, appearance, and duration of surgery in patients with anterior hypospadias. 110 cases were divided into two groups of 56 patients treated by Snodgrass procedure and 54 by Mathieu technique. The meatal stenosis was more common in the Snodgrass group ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.05$, and $p > 0.05$, respectively; X^2 test). There was no difference between groups regarding fistula formation. Mean hospital stay, time to stent withdrawal, and urinary diversion period were shorter in the Mathieu group (7.5 ± 1.19 vs. 5.7 ± 1.38 days, 7.1 ± 0.67 vs. 5.4 ± 0.85 days, and 14.1 ± 1.17 vs. 10.2 ± 1.72 days, respectively; $p < 0.001$ for all). The total success rates were similar (78.6% in the Snodgrass group and 77.8% in the Mathieu group). In a study by Mahmoudreza Moradi [27]. Mean operative time was 94 ± 26.06 minutes and 106.11 ± 23.04 minutes in Mathieu and Snodgrass groups, respectively. Mean stenting duration was 5.06 ± 1.31 days and 5.11 ± 1.56 days in Mathieu and Snodgrass groups, respectively. Hospital stay was 3.93 ± 1.86 days in Mathieu group and 4.55 ± 1.29 days in

Snodgrass group. Statistical analysis showed no differences between the two groups, Success rate was 80.02% in Snodgrass group and 94.45% in Mathieu group ($P > 0.05$). Comparing our study with other studies Anwar-ul-Haq [28], A.M Kajbafzadeh[29],(table-2,3), when they concluded according their results mentioned in both tables that TIP urethroplasty has become a preferred method for repairing distal hypospadias because of its versatility, to correct different meatal variants, the simplicity of the operative technique, low complication rate and reliable creation of a normal appearing glanular meatus. Severe chordee and unhealthy urethral plate are the two limiting factors for this procedure. Fistula can be avoided by interposition of a vascularized dartos flap between the neourethra and overlying skin.

In one study the authors concluded that the TIP was associated with lower complications rate vs. Mathieu technique and that the cosmetic results were far more satisfactory with the TIP operation [30]. Oswald J concluded that the resultant meatus was slit-like in all patients undergoing the Snodgrass repair whereas those with a Mathieu repair had a rounded and horizontal meatus.

Conclusion: The overall complication rate was slightly lower and the surgery was significantly quicker with the Snodgrass urethroplasty. which also had a better cosmetic outcome. The Snodgrass technique is recommended as a primary treatment for distal hypospadias [31]. Combining the Mathieu procedure with plate incision could be considered as a promising simple technique to achieve a normally shaped meatus and to reduce the rate of meatal-related complications; we recommend the major concern with the Snodgrass procedure

	Our study	Aminsharifi [25]	Imamoglu [26]	Mahmoudreza [27]	Anwar-ul-Haq[28]	Amr [32]	Kajbafzadeh [29]
Mean operative time in minute	77 ± 13.03	95		106.11	80	95	
Mean stenting duration (days)	5.01 ± 1.06		5.4 ± 0.85	5.11			5.15
Mean Hospital stay (days)	3.55 ± 1.29		5.7 ± 1.38	4.55	2.5		5.15
Wound breakdown (%)	4.5 (n=4)			0	1.1	9	0
Meatal stenosis (%)	4.5 (n=4)	10			5.5	6.5	0
Proximal urethral stricture (%)	9 (n=9)		8.9	5.66	2.2		
Wound dehiscence (%)	4.5 (n=4)		5.3				0
Urocutaneous (%) fistula	4.5 (n=4)	15	7.1	13.32	3.3	4.6	6 %

Table (3): The results in our study and six studies used Snodgrass technique

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Evaluation of the effect of diagnostic X-ray in the improvement of the outcome of active safe chronic suppurative otitis media

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Abstract

Objective: To evaluate the impact of diagnostic mastoid X-ray in the improvement of the outcome of active safe chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM).

Study Design: Retrospective study, for two groups of patients.

Materials and Methods: A total of 270 patients with safe active CSOM were managed by routine aural toilet, antibiotics and decongestant, divided in to two groups, those who were not exposed to diagnostic x-ray (Group I) and those who were exposed to diagnostic mastoid x-ray (group II).

Setting: Oto-Rhino-Laryngological Department in Mosul General Hospital and Al-Rahma hospital during the period from January 2002 to December 2004.

Results: The final result after 10-15 weeks of follow-up indicated that 50% of patients had complete dryness of the ear from discharge in those exposed to diagnostic X-ray and Only 25% of those not exposed to diagnostic X-rays showed complete dryness of the ear, (p-value =

0.000) which is statistically a significant result.

Conclusion: Some patients with active safe CSOM may get benefit from exposure to diagnostic mastoid X-rays.

Key words: chronic suppurative otitis media, diagnostic mastoid X-rays, bacteria radiation-effects.

Introduction

CSOM is a commonly occurring disease .An incidence of 0.6% among the adult population in UK has been reported [1, 2].In this study it constituted about 7% of patients consulting Oto-Rhino-Laryngological out patient's Department. Aural discharge and impaired hearing are the main presenting symptoms. Energetic local medical treatment changed about 70% of the cases from active phase to inactive [1]. Treatment of CSOM has two main objectives; first to arrest disease and second to secure conditions that would permit return of tissues to normal or that will allow recovery of function [1].

Special regime of local medical treatment (described later) and exposure to diagnostic X-rays showed the improvement of the outcome, and this finding prompted us to conduct this study.

Materials and Methods

Retrospective study of the records of 270 patients with clinical diagnosis of unilateral safe active CSOM were selected from a large number of cases, according to the following criteria:

1. The age between 4-45 years. Patients above 45 years of age could have other medical problems.
2. History of discharging ear at least for 3 months with no improvement in spite of 3-6 times treatment in the usual classical method, with no history of exposure to diagnostic mastoid or skull X-rays.

During the first visit all the patients were treated by aural toilet, decongestant, and the antibiotics (according to culture) given to all patients according to body weight. 128 patients (Group II) had been sent for X-ray of the mastoid (left or right lateral oblique view) in a dose (65 kV, 0.063 sec and 200 mA), about 1-rad= (0.01Gy) as part of diagnosis to exclude mastoiditis. 142 patients (Group I) were not exposed to diagnostic X-ray. During the follow-up in the second, third, and fourth attendance, the patients were examined in the Oto Rhino Laryngological Department and the results were recorded. The following three attendances were arranged 3-4 weeks, 7-8 weeks and 10-15 weeks, respectively.

All the patients were examined in the second visit, 245 patients in the third visit and 225 patients in fourth visit,

respectively and the result were recorded in (Table 1), the reduction in the sample size was nearly equal in both groups and this reduction was probably due to the number of patients being cured and did not attend the clinic for follow up.

Results

During the second visit 122 patients had dry ears, while the remaining patients continued to have wet ears. In third visit, 245 patients were examined :

; 77 patients were still having dry ears In the forth visit (Table 1) , 225 patients were examined; 102 patients from group II and the remaining 123 patients from group I. A total of 80 patients continued to have dry ears and their tympanic membrane healed or had started to heal

Fifty one patients out of the 80 patients with dry ears examined in the fourth visit (end of the follow-up) had been exposed to diagnostic x-ray group II and only 29 patients were not exposed to diagnostic x-ray group I, 70 patients out of these 80 patients with dry at the end of follow-up their age < 12 and 46 of them were male Table1 and 2. Group I, 142 patients, 72 male, 70 female, 53 patients their age < 12 and 89 patients > 12 years. Group II, 128 patients, 74 male, 54 female, and 72 patients their age <12 and 56 patient> 12 years.

Discussion

The value of diagnostic mastoid X-rays in the management of patients with safe CSOM especially those resistant to the classical treatment is to exclude extension of the infection to the mastoid air cells[1,2], in our study the result of diagnostic X-rays proved to be normal.

Group	4 th visit	Dry ear (total)	Dry ear age <12	Dry ear age > 12	Dry ear (female)	Dry ear (male)
Group I (with out x-ray)	123	29 (24%)	26 (90%)	3 (10%)	12 (51%)	17 (59%)
Group II (with x-ray)	102	51 (50%)	44 (86%)	7 (14%)	22 (43%)	29 (57%)
Total	225	80 (36%)	70 (88%)	10 (12%)	34 (42%)	46 (58%)
P-value		0.000	0.660			0.878

Table (1): The result of the two groups of patients in the fourth visit regarding the dryness, ages and sex.

	<12	>12	Total
Dry ear(with & without x-ray) (group I-II)	70 (87.5%)	10 (12.5%)	80
Wet ear (with & without x-ray) (group I-II)	34 (23.5%)	111 (76.5%)	145
Total	104	121	225

Table (2): The outcome of the treatment in regarding to the age of the patients at the end of follow- up.

The 2 groups of patients received routine aural toilet, decongestant and antibiotics according to culture and sensitivity and audiometry 3-6 times before, but the only difference was the exposure of group II patients to the diagnostic X-ray, which surprisingly gave this results. From 142 patients (group I) follow up were continued for 123 of them, 24% of patients their ears became dry, 90% of them their age < 12 years and 59% were male. In 128 patients (group II) in this , follow up was continued for only 102 patients, 51 of them had good improvement which constitute 50%, 44 of them their age < 12 years 86% and 29 of them were male 57% (Table 1).

The reduction in the sample was nearly equal in both groups and these constitute 15%.

Data were analyzed by standard chi-square methods and results were considered statistically significant (p-value = 0.000) in regarding to the benefit of diagnostic mastoid X-ray (Table1&3), not significant in regarding the age group <12 and the sex (p-value = 0.660, 0.878) respectively (Table 1). Odd ratio (OR) shows that the risk of getting no improvement in the patients is more than three-fold in-group I in compared with group II (Table3).

	Wet ear	Dry ear	Total
Group I (Without x-ray)	94 (76.5%)	29 (23.5%)	123
Group II (With x-ray)	51 (50%)	51 (50%)	102
Total	145	80	225

Table (3): The result of the management at the end of follow up in regarding to the exposure to the diagnostic x-rays. OR=3.24

There was good response to treatment in both groups I and II in < 12 years age patients (p-value = 0.000) (Table 2), this could be because patients aged < 12 years receive good attention from their parents to get dry ear, so they adhered to the management and follow-up.

Radiation is one of the most important physical agents used for sterilization[3,4] wound disinfections[5,6]or it can reduce the number of bacteria in vivo[7,8]and in vitro[9].In an other study on the biological effect of single small dose of ionizing x–ray radiation in vitro, has been conducted at Mosul General hospital in Mosul - Iraq for the period from January 2004 – January 2005, the results were significant on certain bacteria[9], Table 4.

The bacteria	Dose of radiation (dose of 0.01 Gy)	T-value
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	45 kv	5.439*
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	45 kv	3.561*
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	45 kv	3.515*
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	45 kv	2.944*
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	45 kv	1.765
<i>Streptococcus faecalis</i>	45 kv	1.643

Table 4: T- Value of the number of viable cells of microorganism pre- post exposure to X - ray of 45 kV (dose of 0.01Gy=1 Rad) of ionizing radiation. * Statistically significant (p < 0.05)

The small doses of the diagnostic X-rays may alter the nature of cells in the mastoid or kill the bacteria [10, 11] or increase the sensitivity of bacteria to

antibiotic [13, 14] or relive functional disorder [15]

Conclusion

Single diagnostic x- ray exposure of mastoid air cells for patients with active safe CSOM in addition to the usual management (mentioned above) could improve the outcome of this disease in some patients.

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Protein-calorie malnutrition in developed countries

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Abstract

Worldwide, over 70 million children suffer from moderate and severe acute malnutrition. Whereas inadequate intake from food insecurity is the primary means by which Protein-calorie malnutrition (PCM) occurs in developing regions, malnutrition in industrialized countries often develops as a complication of underlying illness. The aim of this paper is to briefly review key points regarding diagnosis and management of PCM and to discuss PCM in developed countries.

Keywords: Malnutrition, marasmus, kwashiorkor, developed countries, developing world.

Introduction

Protein-calorie malnutrition (PCM) exists when insufficient energy and/or protein is available to meet an individual's metabolic demands, leading to impairment in normal physiologic processes. Inadequate dietary intake, increased metabolic demands, and increased nutrient losses are important mechanisms involved in the pathogenesis of PCM. Both macronutrient and micronutrient deficiency may be present. While certain adult and elderly populations are at high risk, young children are

particularly susceptible due to significant energy requirements for growth and reliance on others for food delivery. Worldwide, over 70 million children suffer from moderate and severe acute malnutrition[1]

PCM has traditionally been classified according to phenotypic appearance and degree of severity. In children, two distinct types exist: marasmus and kwashiorkor. Marasmic children are thin and have little subcutaneous fat (Figure 1). Wasting is especially evident at the shoulders, buttocks, arms, and thighs. Three categories of acute severity are recognized based on Weight-for-height (W: H) ratios. Mild forms are characterized by a W:H ratio that is 80–90% of normal, moderate disease by a W: H ratio of 70-79%, and severe malnutrition by a W: H ratio less than 70% (corresponding to greater than three standard deviations below the mean) [2].

Key features of kwashiorkor are bilateral pedal edema, anasarca, and irritability (Figure 2).

Figure (1): A child with marasmus

Figure (2): A child with kwashiorkor

Children's hair is often sparse, brittle, and reddish in color. Weight is normal or elevated due to increased body fluid from generalized edema. In the past, kwashiorkor was thought to develop from relative protein deficiency, but this hypothesis has been disputed [3].

Aside from its obvious effects on growth and physical development, PCM has profound consequences on multiple organ systems (Table 1). Malnutrition weakens immune function and predisposes to bacterial, viral, and parasitic infections including pneumonias, urinary tract infections, and sepsis [4]. In tropical regions, measles and malaria are potentially fatal co-morbidities. Anemia, hypoglycemia, diarrhea, and impaired cognition are other frequent effects.

Diagnosis of PCM is most frequently implicated by (1) an abnormally low W: H ratio indicating marasmus, [2] clinical markers of kwashiorkor including pedal edema, or (3) a mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC) less than 125 millimeters. MUAC is a simple, inexpensive, rapid screening tool for PCM. In children 1-5 years of age a mid-upper arm circumference greater than 125 mm is normal; 110-125 mm corresponds to a state of mild or moderate malnutrition; and less than 110 mm corresponds to severe malnutrition.

In adults, MUAC less than 200 is suggestive of PCM. Triceps skin-fold thickness is also used for measuring malnutrition in some populations. In many parts of the world PCM is a clinical diagnosis and management proceeds without extensive laboratory evaluation. Serum chemistries, when performed, may reveal hypernatremia,

hypokalemia, hypocalcaemia, hypophosphatemia, and hypomagnesemia. Plasma albumin is frequently decreased, as is blood urea, transferrin, and cortisol. Chest radiography may expose pneumonia, cardiomegaly, or tuberculosis (in at-risk settings).

Lessons from resource-limited settings

Many methods used in treating patients with PCM stem from experience in developing countries where malnutrition is endemic and constitutes a major underlying factor in approximately 5 million deaths annually [1].

Table 1: Common systemic effects of protein-calorie malnutrition

Organ System	Effect
Immunologic	Impaired cell-mediated immunity and diminished antibody responses
Gastrointestinal	Compromised integrity of GI mucosa causing diarrhea and malabsorption
Endocrine	1. Decreased glycogen stores (from muscle loss and hepatocellular damage) and increased glucose utilization (from infection and impaired thermoregulation) causing hypoglycemia 2. Delayed puberty from altered hypothalamic-pituitary axis function⁵
Hematologic	Iron deficiency anemia and lymphopenia
Musculoskeletal	1. Subcutaneous fat and muscle wasting 2. Nutritional rickets from vitamin D deficiency
Cardiac	Weakened myocardial function, anemia, and dehydration (hypovolemia) leading to congestive heart failure
Neurologic	Impaired cognition and psychosocial development

Management is two-tiered and focused on (1) aggressive identification and treatment of potentially life-threatening conditions associated with PCM including dehydration, infection, electrolyte imbalance, hypoglycemia, hypothermia, anemia, and cardiac failure; and (2) nutritional rehabilitation.

Commonly utilized markers of dehydration (i.e. dry mucous membranes, lack of tears, and skin tenting) are not valid in children with PCM who have atrophied tear ducts and poor supporting subcutaneous

tissue mass. Oliguria and a sunken fontanelle are more reliable indicators

in these patients. When present, dehydration should be corrected slowly. Poor immune function may make identification of superimposed infection difficult since fevers, swelling, and redness are often absent. For this reason, empiric antibiotics should be administered in cases of severe malnutrition. Blood transfusions are considered in the presence of severe anemia (hemoglobin <4-6 g/dL) and adequate immunization status should be confirmed (PCM is not a contraindication to vaccination).

For children, initial dietary treatment usually provides 100 kcal/kg/d and 3 gms/kg/d of protein. When this regimen is tolerated, ideally within a week, caloric load is advanced to at least 200 kcal/kg/d and 5 gms/kg/d of protein. Small quantity, frequent feedings are preferred.

Many nutritional programs supplement with vitamins and micronutrients including vitamin A, folate, iron, and zinc, which may decrease duration of diarrhea if present. In some instances, low-lactose formulas may also be helpful in decreasing diarrhea owing to disaccharidase deficiency associated with malnutrition. Target growth is 10-15 gms/kg/d. If this rate is not attained, potential complications of malnutrition such as infection and anemia, which may impede growth, should be actively investigated. Refeeding of adults with PCM should occur slowly and, whenever possible, in consultation with a nutritionist

Children are discharged from a nutritional rehabilitation program when the W:H ratio is greater than 85%, nutritional edema has resolved, at least one week of consistent weight gain has been achieved, and disease conditions associated with PCM have been addressed. Adults should obtain a minimal body mass index (BMI) of 18.5 kg/ m². Compromised immune function returns to normalcy with recovery although behavioral and mental issues may persist following treatment of severe cases. Prognosis is excellent when PCM is identified early and managed appropriately. In other instances, mortality varies between 15% and 40%. Fatalities in the early days of treatment usually result from

electrolyte imbalance, infection, hypothermia, or circulatory failure. Lethargy, anorexia, stupor, and petechiae are ominous signs.

Burden of disease in developed countries

Whereas inadequate intake from food insecurity is the primary means by which PCM occurs in developing regions, malnutrition in industrialized countries more frequently develops as a complication of underlying illness.

Children with cerebral palsy and other neurodevelopmental impairments are well known to be at high risk of malnutrition as a result of oral-motor dysfunction and gastrointestinal disturbances. Growth is so poor in many of these children that percutaneous gastrostomy is now a common intervention. PCM may be a consequence of hypercatabolic states including burns, trauma, and prolonged febrile disease. Malabsorptive or maldigestive processes such as is seen in children with cystic fibrosis have been associated with undernutrition.

Protein-losing enteropathy, nephrotic syndrome, and enteric fistulas can constitute predisposing conditions, as can metabolic disease such as diabetes and hyperthyroidism. Anorexia nervosa, chronic cardiac disease, renal failure, and transplantation are additional risk factors. Elderly with frail physical conditions, poor cognitive function, and depression are at high risk. Malnutrition may also be common, but difficult to recognize, in general hospital populations [6]. Prevalence reports from the U.S. estimate that PCM affects as

many as 11-61% of hospitalized adults and elderly [7].

Given that the nutritional care of children with physical and mental disabilities is challenging in the best of circumstances, the risk of undernourishment in these children is high in settings where resources are even moderately limited. Institutionalized children with cerebral palsy and other neurodevelopmental impairments, including those living in orphanages or long-term medical facilities, frequently suffer from oropharyngeal dysphagia, aversive feeding behaviors, gastroesophageal reflux, and constipation [8, 9]. As a result, nutritional intake is diminished and eating time is increased, stressing caregivers who have only a fixed timeframe in which to feed many children [10]. The malnutritive state that follows further depresses children's physical strength and cognitive function, and leads to a downward health spiral. Charts illustrating normal growth in children with moderate-to-severe cerebral palsy are now available [11].

Conclusion

While the global burden of PCM falls disproportionately among populations in the developing world, many children in developed countries, such as those with cerebral palsy or other neurological impairments, remain at high risk. The management of patients with malnutrition has been well described and dramatic improvements in weight and physical well-being can be achieved through simple interventions. Recognition of the disease is the first step towards appropriate management and positive outcomes.

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Recent advances in the radiological workup of acute ischemic stroke

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Abstract

Acute stroke is one of the leading causes of mortality and morbidity in adults. The first step in the management of stroke is the establishment of correct diagnosis. Computed Tomography (CT) is the method of choice in the initial workup of acute stroke. However the introduction of multidetector CT and new generations of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has made it possible to perform dynamic and functional analysis of cerebral circulation beside the improvement in the morphological assessment of brain parenchyma and cerebral vessels. The aim of this paper is to review the modern radiological modalities used in the investigation of acute ischemic stroke, enriched with genuine image gallery.

Keywords: Imaging update, Ischemic stroke, CT-perfusion, CT-Angiography, Diffusion weighted images, Perfusion weighted images.

Introduction

According to world health organization (WHO) 15 million people worldwide suffer acute stroke annually. Of these, 5 million are left permanently disabled [1]. The WHO estimates 5.5 million deaths from stroke worldwide in 2001 [2]. In Europe the annual incidence of stroke

Is estimated to 1.1 million in 2000 and suspected to increase to 1.5 million in 2025 [3]. In USA more than 11 million persons sustained stroke in 1998, of whom approximately 770,000 were symptomatic and 11 million were first-ever silent MRI infarcts or hemorrhages [4]. Computed tomography (CT) is the method of choice in the initial workup of stroke [5] with the primary task to exclude intracranial hemorrhage. Early ischemic changes (EICs) on CT were systematically reviewed [5] and to be looked for also in the baseline CT. However there is some controversy on the reliability and prognostic value of EICs on CT [6–7]. Intravenous recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (tPA) is an important evidence based therapy of the acute ischemic stroke [8–9] with treatment started within 3 hours from the onset of stroke but has also shown to achieve some functional improvement in stroke patients when treatment started within 6 hours from the onset of stroke provided initial CT did not reveal extended infarct signs [10]. Although this type of therapy has resulted in significant improvement of the outcome in ischemic stroke, the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS) has

estimated the rate of symptomatic intracerebral hemorrhage to be 6.4% within 36 hours after the onset of stroke [8]. The introduction of such therapy is not possible if patients with symptoms of stroke do not seek acute stroke unit as soon as possible after debut of symptoms. Education and general public information is an essential part of the management of acute stroke. In view of the above mentioned facts a prompt and accurate diagnosis of the underlying cause of the cerebrovascular accident (CVA) and the extent of ischemic injury has become an essential initial step in the management of acute stroke.

The aim of this work was to comprehensively review the recent modalities in the workup of acute ischemic stroke with focus on the indications, technical issues, interpretation of the findings and their clinical implications.

Baseline non-enhanced brain CT

The baseline CT should be performed without delay upon arrival to the emergency unit after the onset of stroke symptoms. The EICs on CT include loss of insular ribbon (Figure 1A), obscuration of sylvian fissure, cortical sulcal effacement, obscuration of lentiform nucleus, loss of gray and white matter differentiation in the basal ganglia and focal hypoattenuation. The hyperdense middle cerebral artery sign (Figure 1B) is another important sign to be looked for in the initial CT in the acute ischemic stroke and was described first in 1983 [11] and recently evaluated and redefined both subjectively and objectively [12].

CT-Perfusion(CTP)

Indications: In many stroke units CTP and CT-Angiography are performed after the non-enhanced brain CT as

integral part of the initial workup of acute stroke provided that radiographers and the radiologists are familiar with the procedures, the postprocessing and the interpretation. Other indications for CTP and CTA are (1) incomplete response to treatment with tPA. (2) Patients with stroke with borderline score on National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) e.g. patients with score of 2-3.

Figure 1: A–B Non-enhanced CT. (A): insula ribbon sign. (B): Hyperdense MCA-sign

(3) Patients who arrived to hospital beyond the therapeutic window for such treatment with tPA (3 hours, recently lengthened to 4.5 hours). (4) Patients with frequently repeated Transient ischemic attacks (TIA). The latter should be considered as serious entity (to be compared with instable angina pectoris in ischemic heart disease) which might culminate into a major stroke. *Technique:* Variable slice thickness can be obtained depending on the scanner type and the number of detectors. In many 16-slice CT-scanners two axial sections with slice thickness of 1.2 cm (up to 4 cm length can be covered in some scanners) can be obtained with the lower cut placed at the level of basal ganglia. This allows assessment of perfusion in all major vessel territories namely territories supplied by middle, anterior and posterior cerebral artery. The recommended scan parameters are: tube voltage 80 Kv, effective tube

current-time product 140-180 mAs, rotation time 0.5 second, cycle time 0.75 second and slice collimation 1.5 mm. Soft tissue algorithm (e.g. Head20) should be used [13,14]. CTP requires a bolus injection of a non-ionic, iodinated contrast agent with an optimal iodine dose of 12 gm (40 ml of 300 mg I/ml or 30 ml of 400 mg I/ml contrast agent) introduced by power injector at flow rate of 8 ml/second (through 16–18 gauge needle) or 6 ml/second (through 20 gauge needle) respectively followed by 40 ml normal saline flush at the same infusion rate. This high infusion rate is required to create optimal color maps and to enable calculation of relative values of Time To Peak (TTP), Cerebral Blood Volume (CBV) and Cerebral Blood Flow (CBF). Other factors that influence image quality are tube voltage (80 Kv gives better contrast/noise ratio and lower radiation dose than 120-140 Kv), slice thickness, and motion artifacts. Postprocessing requires a workstation and perfusion application-software. Two most widely used techniques for calculation of perfusion parameters are the maximum slope model [14,15] and deconvolution model [16].

Interpretation and clinical implementation: Normal brain perfusion is maintained at about 60 ml/100 gm brain tissue/minute by the autoregulatory mechanism of the cerebral vascular bed. The contrast agent introduced during CTP brings about changes in contrast enhancement. Time density curve (TDC) estimation of every single voxel allows calculation of TTP, CBV and CBF. Beside visual assessment of the color maps of TTP, CBV and CBF, relative values of these parameters in region of interest (circular or free-hand), placed in corresponding places of the two cerebral hemispheres, can be determined. The changes in these parameters are

expressed as percentage of reduction of CBV and CBF and prolongation of TTP in the affected side compared with the same values in the healthy side. Upon reduction of cerebral blood flow e.g. thromboembolic occlusion of middle cerebral artery (MCA) the autoregulatory mechanism intervenes to maintain the cerebral blood flow through increasing blood volume in the cerebral vascular bed. The decreased CBF with normal or increased CBV constitute the initial stage of ischemia called “the oligemic phase”. When the autoregulatory mechanism can no longer keep the increased blood volume, a new phase of the so called “tissue at risk” (penumbra) begins (Figure 2A–C). These two phases of ischemia are potentially reversible and brain tissue in question is still salvageable. The role of radiology in finding those reversible changes is a central part of the management in acute ischemic stroke. Penumbra on CT-perfusion considered existing whenever there is discrepancy in the magnitude of the reduction in CBV and CBF. Table 1 shows algorithm for interpretation of CTP in acute ischemic stroke.

Ischemic stage	TTP	CBV	CBF
Oligemic phase	↑	> 80 %	> 60 %
Penumbra (Tissue at risk)	↑	40-80 %	30-60 %
Irreversible ischemic injury	↑	< 40 %	< 30 %
Sever carotis stenosis without ischemia	↑	Normal	Normal

Table (1): Algorithm for interpretation of CTP [14]. Changes in CTP-parameters of the affected side are shown. Reduction CBV and CBF values on the affected side are expressed in percentage compared with those of the normal side.

Figure (2): A–C shows CTP of a patient with left sided hemiplegia, facial palsy and neglect. (A): Increased TTP. (B): Only slight reduction of CBV. (C): Evidently decreased CBF compared with left hemisphere. Because of discrepancy between CBV- and CBF-reduction, perfusion abnormality was graded as tissue at risk in the whole territory of right MCA.

CT-Angiography(CTA)

Indication: This examination is usually performed after CTP in the workup of acute ischemic stroke. Other indications are: (1) evaluation of carotis stenosis/occlusion prior to reconstructive vascular surgery, (2) exclusion of the

possibility of carotis or vertebral artery dissection, and (3) delineation of arteriovenous malformations (AVM) or cerebral aneurysm.

Sinus thrombosis is a rare but deceptive cause of ischemic stroke and usually investigated with CT-angiography of head and skull base.

Technique: This is a helical CT-examination with scan length depending on the clinical question at issue. The scan volume should include the cerebral vessels and carotid arteries beginning either at the aortic arch or just below carotid bifurcation (at the level of C5). The recommended scan parameters are: tube voltage 120 Kv, effective tube current-time product 120 mAs, rotation time 0.5 second, slice collimation 0.75 mm, slice thickness 5 mm (second reconstruction 1 mm, reformatted image thickness 3 mm), feed 9 and increment 0.7 mm. Soft tissue algorithm (e.g. H20–30) should be used [17]. CTA requires a bolus injection of contrast agent: 80–100 ml of 300 mg I/ml contrast agent at flow rate of 4 ml/second followed by 40 ml normal saline flush at the same infusion rate. Start delay of the scan is 15 seconds. Bolus tracking, if available, should be used to optimize the bolus timing and the region of interest (ROI) should be placed in the aortic arch or in the common carotid artery (depending on scan length) with triggering threshold of 120 HU. If bolus tracking is not available a test bolus of 20 ml contrast agent should be introduced to estimate the arrival time. After image acquisition coronal and sagittal reconstruction, preferably with maximum intensity projection (MIP), should be obtained with 3 mm thickness and 3 mm distance between images. 3D-imaging nowadays is widely used postprocessing option. To exclude sinus thrombosis, the same volume of contrast agent and the same

scan parameters and as in CTA can be used with scan delay of 30 seconds.

Interpretation: Every single vessel in the neck and intracranially should be evaluated with regard to occurrence of thrombosis, stenosis/occlusion, dissection, plaque characterization (calcified or cholesterol) and aneurysm (Figure 3A–C).

Figure (3): A–C shows CTA of three different patients. (A) High grade stenosis of the left internal carotid artery caused by both cholesterol and calcified plaque. (B): Thrombosis of basilar artery. (C) 3-dimensional CTA showing aneurysm of basilar top

This requires knowledge of the anatomy of these vessels and the wide range of different normal anatomical variations that may be encountered. The image evaluation should be done on the axial reformatted images and the reconstructed coronal and sagittal images. The CTA-volume can also be used to evaluate the so called “whole brain perfusion” by searching for regions with poor vascular filling in different territories. Furthermore CTA enables studying the collateral circulation. *CT as a method* has the advantage of being available (suppose to be available) on 24-hours basis in almost all hospitals with acute stroke units, easy and rapid to perform and relatively cheap. Almost all radiologists are (suppose to be) able to interpret CT-images and should be familiar with EICs in acute stroke. The major drawback of CT is exposure to ionizing radiation and the side effects of contrast agents in form of renal function impairment and the possibility of allergic reaction. Vital indication should exist before deciding to administer contrast agent in patients with GFR of < 40 and administration of contrast to such patient should be followed by rehydration and monitoring of fluid balance. The total radiation dose delivered in non-enhanced CT, CTP and CTA amounts to about 6-7 mSv. This a considerable dose (especially if repeated) with regard to the carcinogenic effect associated with radiation exposure.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

MRI plays an important role in the workup of stroke. MRI has the advantage of not exposing the patients to ionizing radiation and providing better morphological evaluation especially of the posterior cranial fossa. The major drawback of MRI is the availability of MR-scanner, high cost, long

examination time and interpretation difficulties. Not all stroke centers have access to MRI on 24-hours basis and not all radiologists are familiar with MRI. Patients with pacemaker, metal clips (treated aneurysm) and metal foreign bodies such as missile splinters can not be examined with MRI. Routine MR-sequences reveal EICs at least 6 hours after the onset of stroke. EICs are often impossible to differentiate from widespread changes in the white matter [“unidentified bright objects” UBOs] used to be seen on MRI in elderly patients. Routine MR-sequences include the following sequences: T1 sagittal images, T1 axial images, T1-tse axial images and Fluid-attenuated inversion recovery (FLAIR)-axial images.

Diffusion Weighted Images (DWI):

Indications: DWI is strongly indicated when cerebellar infarcts, brainstem infarcts and lacunar infarcts are suspected. Other indications include persistent neurological deficit in patients with major stroke or TIA whose baseline CT was normal or difficult to interpret e.g. widespread white matter changes. None-responder to thrombolytic therapy is another patient category that usually examined with DWI. DWI should be done together with the routine MR-sequences and not unusually combined with Perfusion Weighted Images (PWI) and 3-dimensional Time-Of-Flight Angiography(3DTOF).

Technique: This MR sequence is very sensitive to early ischemic injuries. Changes in this sequence can be seen few minutes after the onset of stroke. Echo-planar DWI include axial DWI (diffusion gradient applied at 3 directions; b value= 0, 500, and 1000 s/mm^2) and calculation of Apparent Diffusion Coefficient (ADC-map).

Interpretation and clinical implementation: DWI reflects water motion in the extracellular space. Upon ischemic injury the cell membrane-bound Na-K pump cease to function and sodium-water influx into the injured cells causes cellular edema and shrinkage of the extracellular space. This result in restricted diffusion which is expressed as increased signal on DWI-images and decreased ADC-value. These changes can be seen in acute infarcts up to two weeks after the onset and can be correlated to the chronological debut of stroke symptoms. This sequence helps the radiologist to differentiate new infarcts from old infarcts and other changes in the cerebral and cerebellar white matter. In patients not subjected to thrombolytic therapy the detection of

Figure (4): A–D shows MR-diffusion of three different patients with acute infarcts. (A) High DWI-signal and (B) Low ADC-value in a left cerebellar infarct. (C) Low ADC-value in a left brainstem infarct. (D) High DWI-signal in acute lacunar infarct affecting pyramidal tract at the level of right corona radiata of patient with complete left sided hemiplegia.

acute and subacute infarcts by DWI (Figure 4A–D) explains the neurological deficit the patient presented with, can help to plan the rehabilitation, and predict the functional outcome.

Perfusion Weighted Images (PWI):

Indications: The indications mentioned for CTP and DWI can be applied here. MRI means some logistic difficulties in monitoring patients with acute stroke. This makes CTP superior to PWI. However PWI has the advantage of providing perfusion maps of the whole brain.

Technique: PWI are T2*-weighted gradient-echo single-shot EPI sequence performed during a bolus contrast infusion. Gadolinium-based contrast agent at a dose of 0.1 mmol per kilogram body weight should be introduced by a power injector at a rate of 5 ml/second (through 20 gauge needle), followed by 40 ml normal saline flush at the same infusion rate. The PWI sequence started 10 seconds before the infusion of contrast bolus in order to acquire an imaging baseline. Recommended scan parameters for the PWI: TR/TE 2410/49 ms, flip angle 90 degrees, the field of view 220 x 220 mm², and acquisition time 120 seconds. The slice thickness 5 mm with distance factor of 30% (intersection gap of 1.5 mm), and the matrix 128 x 128 (voxel size =1.8 x 1.8 x 5.0 mm³). As in CTP there are different models of interpretation of brain perfusion on MRI. One of the commonly used models is based on deconvolution analysis taking into account the arterial input function (AIF) [18,19]. This requires workstation with access to “Perfusion MR” application. Mean Transit Time (MTT), TTP, CBV and CBF maps can be generated. As in CTP the interpretation is both subjective (visual assessment of color maps) and

objective (measurements of relative values of MTT, TTP, CBV, and CBF). The values are often compared with those of the healthy side.

Interpretation and clinical implementation: As in CTP the aim of PWI is to find salvageable brain tissue, select patients suitable for thrombolysis therapy and plane the patients who are not eligible for thrombolysis therapy (e.g. arrival to stroke unit beyond the therapeutic window) for other form of therapy such as other anticoagulant therapy, hypothermia etc with a major aim to limit the extent of the ischemic injury and improve the functional outcome. Tissue at risk (penumbra) on

Figure (5): A–C shows PWI and D shows DWI of one patient with left sided hemiplegia. (A): Increased TTP in the right MCA and ACA-territory. (B): Normal CBV. (C): Markedly reduced CBF. (D) DWI shows limited region of restricted diffusion (high DWI-signal) beside the lateral ventricle (arrow, D). The region marked with P is the region that shows perfusion defect on A–C without any diffusion abnormality on D. Region marked P considered as salvageable tissue with ischemic penumbra.

MRI is, unlike CT-penumbra, evaluated on both DWI and PWI. Regions of restricted diffusion on DWI develop likely into infarcts i.e. irreversible changes. Difference in volume of the deficit on PWI and the volume of the restricted diffusion represent penumbra or “tissue at risk” on MRI (Figure 5A–D).

Summary

Intravenous thrombolysis therapy is an evidence based therapy of the acute ischemic stroke that is associated with improved functional outcome but also carries some risk of symptomatic intracerebral hemorrhage. Hereby a correct diagnosis is very crucial for the proper selection of patients for thrombolysis therapy. Non-enhanced CT should thus be considered as inadequate diagnostic tool in the modern stroke management.

Complementary information about tissue perfusion and the cerebral vascular tree can be provided by different methods. A combination of CTP and CTA fulfill all the requirements for acute stroke imaging [20]. CT has the advantage of better availability, ease to perform and interpret, lower cost and short examination time. In general perfusion studies (CTP or PWI) help to define infarct core and detect tissue at risk that can be salvaged by appropriate treatment whereas angiography (CTA or 3D TOF) help to define the occlusion site, study collateral circulation and exclude arterial dissection or sinus thrombosis. Wintermark et al [21] showed that perfusion CT allows accurate prediction of the final infarct size and subsequently predict the clinical outcome of acute stroke. Diffusion weighted images are the method of choice in cases with persistent neurological deficit after thrombolysis treatment as well as in

cases with suspected cerebellar or brainstem infarcts and in supratentorial lacunar- and watershed infarcts. These new modalities require modern multidetector CT, power injector, and workstation for postprocessing purposes. They have to be performed only in stroke center when trained radiographer, trained radiologists and neurologists are available.

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An Evaluation of temporomandibular Joint disc position in temporomandibular disorders by magnetic resonance imaging

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Abstract

Objectives: The aim of this study is to evaluate disc position and the type of disc displacement, intra-capsular effusion and degenerative changes of the condyle using MRI technique.

Materials and Methods: 84 TMJs of 42 patients with TMJ disorders were studied in Al Kadhimiya Teaching Hospital during the period from April 2004 to November using clinical examination and MRI. The angle between the posterior margin of the disc and vertical drawn through the center of the condyle was measured on MRI for each TMJ.

Results: 74 TMJs were found to have internal derangement (ID) and 10 TMJs were found to be normal without disc derangement (No DD). The positions of the disc were: Normal (0-10) in 7.4%, slightly displaced (11-30) in 24.8%, mildly displaced (31-50) in 10.5% and moderately displaced (51-80) in 4.76%. TMJs with ADWR – disc was severely displaced interiorly (over 80) and TMJs with ADWOR-constituting (18.52) % of all cases.

Conclusion: the current study confirm that the smaller the degree of disc displacement the milder the internal

derangement and that the intra-capsular effusion was more frequently associated with TMJ with ADWR. The degenerative condylar changes were more severe with an increased degree of anterior disc displacement.

Keyword: Temporomandibular disorders, disc displacement, MRI.

Introduction

Temporomandibular joint (TMJ) internal derangement is has been linked with some controversy as to degenerative arthropathies [1, 2, 3]. Fibrous tissues fraying may be an inciting factor for disc displacement. Most frequently the disc displaced anteriorly, either as anterior disc displacement with reduction (ADWR) or anterior disc displacement without reduction (ADWOR) but there is a high incidence of medial or lateral displacement. Gross comparison of the morphologic appearance of normal TMJs with that of joints with TMJs with disc displacement suggest that disc displacement is the predisposing factor that leads to the degenerative changes of the articular surfaces and perforation of the disc or posterior attachment [4]. The effect of the degree of anterior disc displacement on the formation of intra-capsular effusion is questionable [5,6]. Spurring, flattening and erosion along

the condylar surface, glenoid fossa, or articular eminence were classified as degenerative changes on MRI obtained[7].The aim of this study is to evaluate the type of disc displacement to intra-capsular effusion and degenerative changes of the condyle using Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI).

Materials and methods

Eighty four TMJs of forty two patients (32 female and 10 male) who had TMJ disorders were included in the study. MRI images were obtained in addition to clinical examinations. Patients aged 16-55 years with mean \pm SD of 30.5 \pm 16. TMJ images were taken from 1.5 T gyroscany using 140 mm field of view a 256 x 256 matrix and 3-mm slice thickness with spin echo surface coil at T1A, TR, 2000 Milliseconds TE 8-6\ 12 milliseconds. The images were obtained in the coronal-oblique and sagittal-oblique planes at the closed and open-mouth positions as shown in figure 1. Measurements of the signal intensity were made directly on the MR imager for the T2-weighted images. Intra-capsular effusion was detected on MRI with T2 weighted images as can increased signal. The superior position of the disc was regarded as normal positioning and an anterior position from the superior position of the disc was regarded as anterior disc displacement in closed-mouth position. Return to normal condyle and disc relationship in wide opening was regarded as (ADWOR). A line was drawn between the summits of the post glenoid tubercle and the articular eminence, and the mild point of the condylar portion of this line was marked. The angle between the vertical lines that was drawn through the posterior margin of the disc was measured on sagittal MRI for each TMJ.

The degree of anterior disc displacement was classified as follows: 0 – 10 as normal disc position, 11–30 as slight anterior disc displacement, 31–50 as mild anterior disc displacement, 51–80 as moderate anterior disc displacement, over 80 degree as severe anterior disc displacement, this is a similar standardization with previous reports[7,8].

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software (version 10). Frequency and percentage was calculated for each parameter. The relationship among parameter and clinical findings were assessed using Chi – square X^2 test. For all statistical analyses, a *P* – value of < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

The seventy four of the eighty four TMJs were found to have internal derangements Figure-1 shows the method of measuring the angle of disc displacement MRI view of the TMJ (0 degree, superior disc position).

Figure (1): The method of measuring the angle of disc displacement MRI view of the TMJ (0 degree, superior disc position)

The other ten cases of unilateral asymptomatic cases had superior disc position on MRI that regarded as normal cases. Figure-2 shows severe anterior disc displacement (over 80 degree) on

MRI Arrows show the disc. Figure-3 shows intracapsular effusion present in the lateral part of the superior joint space (coronal section). Figure-4 shows the result of the degree distribution of TMJ disc positions in the study group.

Figure 2: Severe anterior disc displacement (over 80 degree) on MRI Arrows show the disc.

Figure (3): Intracapsular effusion (arrow) present in the lateral part of the superior joint space (coronal section).

Figure (4): The result of the degree distribution of TMJ disc positions in the study group.

The disc position was normal in 7.4%, slightly displaced in 24.8 %, mildly

Displaced in 10.5 % ,moderately displaced in 4.9 % of the TMJs with ADWR; while severe anterior disc displacement was observed in all TMJs with ADWOR constituting 18.52% of all (84) TMJs. The remaining two TMJs were found to have pure medial Disc Displacement only. No posterior disc displacement was found in the present study. Using sagittal oblique and coronal sections of MRI, 81.25% of the TMJ internal derangements were pure anterior disc displacements whereas 9.82% of the cases had anteriomedial disc displacement in addition to 1.79% of the cases with pure medial displacement as shown in table -1.

(DD) Disc Displacement	Lateral DD		Medial DD		Neither lateral nor medial DD		Total
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	
ADWR	6	4.7	6	4.7	38	33.92	50
ADWOR	---	---	1	0.62	22	22.40	23
No ADD	---	---	2	1.19	---	---	2
Total	6		9		60		75

Table (1): TMJ disc positions in sagittal oblique and coronal sections on MRI ADWR = anterior displacement with reduction. ADWOR= anterior displacement with out reduction.

Intra-capsular effusion was observed in 19(17.54%) out of 73TMJs with anterior disc displacement but only 1 (4.42%) out of 9 TMJs with normal disc position. Intra capsular Effusion was present in 15 (17.62%) out of 58 TMJs with pain and TMJ pain was present in 15 (51.11%) out of 20 intra-capsular effusions. The relationships of intra-capsular effusion with the disc displacement, TMJ pain and the type of disc displacement were not found to be statistically significant. However, TMJ pain in (ADWOR) was found to be approximately fourfold of (ADWR) cases. Degenerative changes

such as condylar surface flattening and osteophyte formation on the condylar surface in cases of (ADWOR) were found to be significant statistically in comparison with TMJs with reducing discs ($p < 0.025$,

Surface degenerations on condyle.	ADWR	ADWOR	No AD	Pure medial displacement	Total
Present	16	15	0	---	31
Not present	34	8	9	1	52
Total	50	23	9	1	83

Table (2): Statistical analysis of articular surface changes according to the types of displacement ($\chi^2 = 5.4091309$, $p < 0.016$)

Degenerative changes on the condylar surface increased in cases with TMJ (ADWOR) as shown in table-3.

Degree of disc displacement	degenerative changes on the condylar surfaces	
	No.	%
0°-10°	0	0
11°-30°	8	18.44
31°-50°	4	24.56
51°-80°	2	26.26
Over 80°	14	41.90

Table (3): Frequency and percentage of the disc displacement degree and degenerative changes on the condylar surfaces

The results of clinical examination in relation to disc position with disc displacement as shown in table - 4.

Clinical diagnosis	MRI findings			
	No D	ADWR	ADWOR	Total
No D	9	3	---	12
ADWR	---	46	1	47
ADWOR	---	1	22	23
Total	9	50	23	82

Table (4): Frequency of MRI diagnostic results of anterior TMJ disc displacement (MRI findings) versus the clinical evaluation (clinical diagnosis) NoD = no displacement. ADWR = anterior displacement with reduction. ADWOR = anterior displacement with out reduction.

There was statistically significant between MRI findings and clinical examinations in TMJ internal derangement (kappa 0.935) and with TMJs normal disc position were included (kappa 0.885).

Discussion

The current study supported previous reports in the literature that the most frequent disc displacement was anterior[0,10,11], it was indicate that the most frequent abnormal disc position in patients with TMJ disorders was the anterior or the anterolateral and in this study found the medial component to the displacement being more frequent. The concept of disc acting like a wedge suggested a mechanism by which pure lateral and medial displacements could occur. However, in this study pure lateral and medial disc displacements are rather rare. The end result of the hypertrophic responses of bone and disc would be localized decrease in joint space and an alteration on the joint surface and disc, sufficient to cause the disc to begin to act like a wedge and to become displaced in the closed-mouth position. Increased friction of the

articular surfaces and adhesions has been suggested as initiating events that could cause disc displacement. This mechanism could be responsible for anterolateral and anteromedial disc displacements which constituted 9.4% of cases examined in this study that in accordance with the previous study⁽¹²⁾. The posterior disc displacement is extremely uncommon and it was not observed in the present study. Superior disc position is commonly used to refer to normal disc position in the sagittal oblique, closed-mouth view. The most common method used to judge disc position has been the closed-mouth sagittal view assessment of the position of the posterior band relative to the top of the condyle as a superior disc position [7]. Argued that in order to be considered normal, the junction of the posterior band should not be more than 10 from the 12 o'clock position with variability of 0.16+4.6 degrees. This method was devised to quantify meniscus displacement in terms of the number of degree from a 12 o'clock or vertical position in relation to the condyle. The junction of the posterior band of the meniscus and the bilaminar zone should fall within 10 degree of vertical to be within the 95th percentile of normal. In a similar way, that regard the superior position of the disc as being within the limit of 0-10 degree, modifying the same method of the disc position assessment, Silverstein et al., (2001) [5] reported a mean of -3.53+11.12 degree in asymptomatic subjects. However, the vertical reference line which was determined as the long axis of the condyle in their study was slightly different from our references line drawn through the midpoint of the condyle at right angle with another line drawn between the summit of the articular eminence and the post glenoid

process. By using a different reference line drawn perpendicular to the Frankfort horizontal plane, Rammelsberg et al., (1997) [13] reported that 85% of the TMJs had a posterior band that was less than 26.6degree anterior to 12 o'clock position, the average worst case position of the posterior band being 6.4+119.8 degree, that is suggesting an 11 o'clock criterion (30 degree forward) should be considered within normal range. Additional data gathered on the prevalence of disc displacement in asymptomatic subjects with no positive finding for TMD (Temporomandibular disorders) [14, 15, 16]. Hatala et al., (1991) [14] suggest that about a third of apparently normal subjects have silent disc displacements. When the degree of anterior disc displacement from the superior position was between 11 and 80 degree, the discs were reducing whereas in case of disc position over 80 degree, this correlated with non reducing disc on opening. Sagittal and coronal MRI show significant degenerative surface changes such as thickening of the superior cortex of the condyle, condylar surface flattening and osteophyte formation in TMJ ADWOR [17, 18, 19]. More condylar degenerative changes were seen with greater degree of disc displacement, Rudisch et al, (2001) [6] reported a significant relationship between TMJ pain& TMJ effusion on MRI. On the other hand, the presence of intra-capsular effusion constituted only 17.20 %of TMJs with pain with no statistical significance but, TMJ pain was present in 46.71% of TMJs with intracapsular effusion in the present study and this is in agreement with the literature[7,19,20];. The joint effusion seems to occur more frequently in TMJs with ADWR than ADWOR. Emshoff et al, (2001)[2] showed that TMJ pain was related to MRI diagnosis of ADWOR in

comparison with their results, clinical finding of TMJ pain was much more frequent in ADWOR than ADWR detected on MRI in the present study. It was concluded that intra- capsular effusion could cause TMJ Pain; it is obvious that intracapsular effusion plays an important role in TMJ pain but it is not the only source of TMJ pain.

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Persistent trophoblastic disease

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Introduction

Gestational trophoblastic disease (GTD) comprises a range of related tumors arising from tissues of placental origin including complete hydatidiform mole, partial hydatidiform mole, invasive mole, choriocarcinoma and placental site trophoblastic tumor [1]. Complete hydatidiform mole occurs in approximately one in 500 to 2000 pregnancies [2]. The highest rates of gestational trophoblastic disease occur in some developing countries, with rates of 1:125 pregnancies in certain areas of Asia [3].

Persistent trophoblastic disease refers to a disease in women who've had treatment to remove a molar pregnancy but still have persistent molar tissue/activity. Even a very small volume of molar tissue anywhere in the body can grow and cause further problems [4]. It may develop after a molar pregnancy, a non-molar pregnancy or a live birth [5].

The International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) , defines persistent trophoblastic disease as the presence of a plateau in serum hCG concentrations for three weeks, a hCG rise for two consecutive weeks, the detection of hCG 6 months after evacuation, or the histological finding of a choriocarcinoma [6].

Bilateral theca lutein cysts are visible in 20-50% of such cases. Rarely, theca

lutein cysts rupture, hemorrhage, or cause ovarian torsion [7].

Case report

A 34-year-old woman was admitted to the emergency unit with a 2-days history of abdominal pain and discomfort. She gives a history of uterine evacuation of a molar pregnancy 10 days previously. She had no vaginal bleeding at the time of presentation and no vomiting. On examination she was clearly in pain and looked pale with a mild pallor. Her temperature was 36.8 C; PR was 110 with a blood pressure of 100 / 60 mmHg. Abdomen was tense, slightly distended with moderate tenderness and rebound tenderness in the right and left iliac fossa. Uterus could not be palpated per abdomen, with no other abdominal masses. Bimanual examination revealed bilateral adnexal tenderness. There was no cervical excitation and no vaginal bleeding. She didn't have a previous testing of serum β - HCG but on admission the serum β - HCG was 800 iu/l, other routine laboratory tests (including complete blood count, and tests of liver and renal function) were unremarkable. On Trans abdominal US examination there was a right side ovarian cyst 8.4 cm X6.2 cm, and a left side complex adnexal mass 6cm X4.8 cm with a moderate amount of free fluid

in the abdominal cavity. The uterus was bulky with empty uterine cavity. No other pathology detected. The patient was aware that she has bilateral ovarian cyst detected before her uterine evacuation and her doctor inform her that they need no interference and they will resolve spontaneously. A decision of explorative laparotomy was taken for a diagnosis of acute abdomen and suspicion of complicated ovarian cyst. During laparotomy there was serosanguinous fluid in the abdominal cavity with the appearance of bulky uterus, also there was a left ovarian multilocular cyst that is twisted with rupturing of one of the loculi, the cyst was dark and congested. On the right side there was other multilocular ovarian cyst about 8X6 cm with normal color. Untwisting of the left ovarian cyst was done and it was packed with a dressing soaked with warm saline for about 15 minutes. aspiration of the right ovarian cyst failed and we decided to do a cystectomy to prevent further twisting on the right side [Figure-1].

Figure (1): The right ovary enlarged with theca lutein cyst, about 8 cm X 6 cm, with multiple loculi filled with blood clots. Aspiration failed and cystectomy performed with adequate hemostasis.

The cysts were filled with blood clots explaining the failed aspiration. On the left side, the ovary remained dusky in color after 15 minutes from untwisting and soaking with warm saline so a

decision of oophorectomy was taken [Figure 2]. The patient progressed well postoperatively. One week later on, another serum β - HCG was done, and it was also 760 iu/L. the patient failed to attend further follow up, but returned 3 weeks later complaining of cough and haemoptysis. Chest X-ray was negative. Sputum for AFB was negative. Serum β -HCG was 800 iu/ L. Further diagnostic work included a computed tomography (CT) scan of the chest and a CT scan of the abdomen, both could not detect any evidence of metastatic or disseminated disease. A decision of starting chemotherapy with methotrexate was taken jointly with a consultant medical oncologist. The patient responded well, she stopped having haemoptysis and her serum β - HCG dropped to 640 iu/L , then 480 iu/L and became undetectable after 6 weeks of treatment with methotrexate.

Figure (2): The left ovary found to be twisted and dark in color with partial rupture of a theca lutein cyst. The ovary un-twisted and covered by a pack soaked with warm saline for 15 minutes but it didn't return to normal. Oophorectomy was performed.

Discussion

About 15% of complete molar pregnancies are associated with persistent GTD or choriocarcinoma [8]. Biomarkers are very effective in the prediction of persistent trophoblastic disease (PTD). It can identify PTD in a very early stage and if measured before

evacuation, it can detect high risk patients who may develop PTD in future [9].

Chest x-ray is appropriate to diagnose lung metastases. lung CT-scan may be used for staging [10]. However, in our case, no abnormality was detected by neither chest X-Ray nor chest CT-scan. The patient only had a plateau level of serum β -HCG (a biomarker) which predicted the presence of persistent trophoblastic disease and lead to clinically evident symptoms of ovarian hyperstimulation and its subsequent complications. Rising or plateau level of β -human chorionic gonadotropin is likely to be associated with clinical or sub clinical latent persistent trophoblastic disease [11].

Prominent theca lutein ovarian cysts usually develop in about half of all patients with a complete mole due to ovarian stimulation by elevated levels of circulating human chorionic gonadotropin [3, 4, 12, 13, 14].

Ovarian cysts should not be resected nor ovaries removed as spontaneous regression will occur with elimination of the mole [3], with resolution within 8-12 weeks of evacuation. Cysts that persist after beta-hCG levels return to normal should prompt further workup to exclude a neoplastic process as they are considered as pathognomonic of trophoblastic neoplasia [7, 11].

Aspiration of ovarian cysts can be helpful because these cysts are usually filled with amber-colored or serosanguinous fluid [15] but in the present case cystectomy was done because hemorrhage into these ovarian loculi with blood clots which made aspiration impossible.

Post-molar disease occurs in 55% of patients with persistent theca lutein ovarian cysts or uterine size greater than 20 weeks [16]. Patient with theca lutein cysts >6 cm in diameter are considered as high risk for developing post-molar disease; therefore, prophylactic chemotherapy is indicated immediately after evacuation [17, 18]. Other features that require prophylactic chemotherapy are: excessive uterine size and pre-evacuation HCG level >100000 U/l [16, 19]. The use of prophylactic chemotherapy may be particularly beneficial in patients with high-risk complete hydatidiform mole who cannot be followed up effectively [20]. However, some experts still argue against the use of prophylactic chemotherapy because of the risk of drug resistance [21].

Our patient responded very well to single agent chemotherapy (Methotrexate). No further attacks of haemoptysis. MTX is highly effective with a cure rate for molar pregnancies, of >99% [22].

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The development of health informatics profession: An overview of the development in different countries

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The rapid development of health informatics could improve the delivery of healthcare while bad one could kill [1] The relatively short history of health informatics is punctuated with serious steps of development that started by the use computers in almost every aspect of life. The rapid development of health informatics profession in many countries created the need of regulatory bodies to register health informatics professionals, protect the public, and improve health informatics profession.

History of health informatics

Cesnik chronicled the developmental steps of health informatics. At the end of the 1950s, Ledley and Lusted recognized the possible use of computer-assisted medical decision making, but the limitations were high cost and non availability of computers. The invention of microcomputers in late 1960s and later development of these microcomputers in the 1970s and 1980s made computers faster, more powerful, available and not expensive. Medical and nursing informatics started in 1970s, and the use of computer to support making medical decisions became strong in 1980s. The development of integrated systems using new database and networks started in 1989 [2].

Development of global health informatics profession

The definitions of health informatics and e-Health are important for recognizing this field as a profession. Health informatics is "The knowledge, skills and tool which enable information to be collected, managed, used and shared to support the delivery of healthcare and to promote health".[3] E-health is "a new term used to describe the combined use of electronic communication and information technology in the health sector" [4]

The international development of health informatics as a profession that required special education, qualifications, code of conduct, and professional bodies could be traced in the literatures. Ball et al presented the health informatics program provided by the Informatics Task Force in Maryland. This program consisted of informatics modules concentrating on information, technology, and health science that are available at undergraduate and postgraduate levels [5]. Haux and Leven presented the curriculum for a 4.5 year medical informatics course at the University of Heidelberg that covers a wide range of healthcare economics, bio-signal and medical image processing, medical records, and medical information[6,7] Frey et al assessed the job situation for those graduates through a questionnaire,

the response rate was 62.2%, and the results showed 44.5% of them were working within the field of medical informatics; 53.0% were working in the sector of informatics (but not medical informatics); 2.2% were working in other fields and 0.3% did not indicate[8]. Chi and Pavilceck looked for the need of unique curricula with healthcare and computer programs to educate health informatics student and develop graduates [9] Olsson et al, and Doupi et al presented the priority on e-Health in Europe where the European Commission funded about 400 research and development projects in e-Health since 1990 covering the ethical, legal, technical, clinical, origination and marketing issues [10, 11]. The Working Group 1 of the International Medical Informatics Association (IMIA) studied the educational needs of the healthcare professionals (physicians, nurses, and health and medical informatics professionals) for knowledge in information and communication technology; and they recommended establishing courses or complete programs to develop the available educational programs in medicine, nursing, dentistry, pharmacy, healthcare management, public health, health record administration, and computer science all over the world, and recommend offering a certificate for high quality to these courses and programs[12].

There is a growing commitment of governments around the globe to the wide range of possibilities offered by e-Health. The e-Health Conference that was held in Spain in 2006 raised the importance of the 2005 World Health Assembly e-Health Resolution, and the European Commission's e-Health Action Plan [13].

The World Health Organization (WHO) program for e-Health strategy established in 2006 to support all members in identification of the most suitable applications of e-Health, facilitates development of ethical and legal policies related to health informatics, and support the implementation of technical programs in countries. Geissbuhler et al found that collaboration between IMIA and WHO could improve health informatics professionals in the aspects of international observation of health informatics, developing the health care workforce through using ICT, and sharing ideas of e-Health[14].

Development of the health informatics profession in UK

Benjamin et al, and Rigby et al found that the safe and effective use of health informatics depends on the good understanding of the end users of the health informatics systems; and they found that providing European / International Computer Driving License courses for the health professionals was a good way of local training in UK National Health Service (NHS) and could be considered as a reference standard[2,15]. In addition, Benjamin et al confirmed that the proper development of health informatics staff is through creating education and training programs that cover requirement of job roles, which could be through creating academic courses with known learning outcomes, creating seminars, short courses and e-learning for continuous professional development and mentoring and transfer between departments to increase experience[2]. Benjamin et al stated that health informatics professions included several specialties; and all health informatics professionals shared a core of knowledge

and skills and each specialty needs additional knowledge and skills in its field of practice. They classified health informatics professionals in the NHS into; Information and Communication Technology Staff (35.2%); Health Records Staff (26.15%); Information Management Staff (12.8%); Clinical Coding Staff (9.3%); Knowledge Management Staff (4.5%); Education, Training and Development Staff (35.2%); Senior Managers and Directors of Services (2.96%); Clinical Informatics (0.60%)[2].

Development of the health informatics profession in Middle East

The health informatics profession has been steadily developing in the Middle East. There are several postgraduate programs in the fields of health informatics, health records, and/or medical librarianship in Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Oman, and Iran. In addition, there are several health informatics associations in the region, such as the Arab Telemedicine Association, the Lebanese Association of Health Informatics, the Saudi Association of Health Informatics, the Syrian Association of Health Informatics, and the Middle East Association of Health Informatics, which is part of IMIA.

Development of health informatics in Iraq

Health informatics is not yet well recognized as a profession in Iraq, due to the wars. However, the Iraqi ministry of health and Iraqi universities are acting seriously to improve health informatics. The Ministry of Health has adopted several serious programs to introduce the advanced Information and Communication Technology in the daily work of the Ministry of Health and its hospitals and health institutes, and encouraged its health professionals and

administration staff to attend special programs to improve their IT skills. During the period prior to the 2003 war, there was extensive use of computers at the institutes and offices on Ministry of Health for drugs distribution databases, medical library databases using the UNESCO CDS/ISIS software, specialized databases of medical literature especially cancer, the disease registries, the support of Health InterNetwork Access to Research Initiative (HINARI), and the Primary Health Care Centers network which is being built to register patients and diseases in the 18 governorates and at the central level. The Iraqi Ministry of Health has been controlling the medical records, especially the death certificates and birth certificates, very well. These important documents are issued only by hospitals and institutes under control of the Ministry of Health, and copies of them remain at the medical records units of the Ministry of Health. When the data in these documents would be entered into the database system, it would create a huge source of information to assist taking important decisions. This will be one of the important steps for the health informatics professionals to gain respect and recognition in Iraq.

Health Informatics Professional Bodies

As other professions that have regulatory bodies, health informatics professionals created their regulatory bodies with code of conduct. Benjamin et al concluded that the main function of the professional regulation is the provision of high quality health informatics services to improve healthcare delivery (patient centered service) through adherence to code of practice and national values [2]. Madge and Hayes stated that the UK

Council for Health Informatics Professions (UKCHIP) was founded in September 2002 to be the regulatory body of all specialties of health informatics. Its primary function is to keep a register of health informatics professionals and to de-register anyone who fails to maintain the required professional standards (behavior and continuous personal development). There are three levels of registration (level 1-Registered Health Informatician; level 2- Advanced Health Informatician; level 3- Principle Health Informatician) that depends on qualification, employment profile, and length of times served healthcare and in informatics. Registration is so far voluntary. The UKCHIP is aiming to encourage the use of informatics to promote healthcare; to improve qualification and training of health informatics professionals; and to protect the public [16].

Conclusion: In the last few decades, the huge development of IT that makes computers fast, powerful, available and not expensive led to the introduction computers and networks in almost every aspect of life, including healthcare. The use of informatics in providing healthcare services encourages researchers to study its advantages and disadvantages. It was concluded that good health informatics improve health services, while bad health informatics might kill patients. Therefore, education institutes and health authorities in many countries have been encouraging health professionals to improve their IT skills. This led to the recognition of health informatics profession as a distinct professional field that includes several specialties.

The health professional bodies are regulatory bodies that aim to register and develop its professionals, enhance the

benefits of health informatics, and avoid its hazards and protect the public.

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Research Archive: Escherichia coli as a bacterial indicator of potential health hazards associated with food handlers in Samarra city

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Many important health researches in Iraq have been lost during the past decades because of the lack of documentation. We believe that The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has played an important role during the previous years in documenting Iraqi medical work and making the available to international researchers.

The aim of this paper is to report the use of a new approach during 1990s for food handlers examination prior to their employment and the utilization of Escherichia Coli as a bacterial indicator of potential health hazards associated with food –handlers in Samarra city in 1990s. 200 food handlers were examined whilst at work (in –use test) in Samarra city during April, May and June 1994 ,they were restaurants workers, butchers and dairy workers and their numbers were 137,48 and 15 respectively. The mid- finger of both right and left hands of the food handlers were immediately and thoroughly rinsed in universal bottles containing sterile MacConkey broths while they were carrying their different works responsible for. The process of rinsing fingers was rapidly made to avoid any sort of contamination from the environment and without prior cleaning or washing of the hands. No pre-arrangements were made with food-handlers for the time of taking samples). The universal bottles containing samples

were incubate at 37 c for 24 hours. Inoculated MacConkey broth containing universal bottles were used as control. After the incubation period the bottles were examined for lactose fermentation. A loopful sample from each fermented broth was taken and inoculated on a MacConkey agar No.3 (oxid) plates. The inoculated plates were incubated at 37c for 24 hours and the suspected E.Coli were observed. The suspected E Coli colonies were sub cultured in MacConkey broth containing Durham tubes and incubated at 37c for 24 hrs and the production of acid and gas was recorded.

The same selected colonies were sub cultured in tryptophane water and incubated at 37 c for 24 hrs. and few drops of Kovac's reagent were added to each tube and the formation of pinkish rings was considered as an indication of Indole production. The isolates produced acid, gas and Indole were considered as human derived E coli Food contamination is a problem in Samarra city as more than 40% of food handlers are having fecally contaminated hands. That study was relatively new approach for assessing the hygienic condition of food-handlers.

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